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Future Circular Collider

DELIVERABLE REPORT

ANALYSIS OF THE REQUIREMENTS AND OPTIONS FOR AN ADDITIONAL FCC POLE

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GLOSSARY:

All of the abbreviations used in this document are available and kept up to date in the online glossary <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/GlossaryOfTerms>.

SUMMARY

The purpose of the feasibility study of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) is to develop a concept for a new research infrastructure to accommodate the next generation of higher-performance particle colliders designed to extend the research currently being carried out at the LHC once the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) research programme concludes in around 2040.

This underground infrastructure would be located in an area spanning the Swiss/French border. Eight access sites are planned at regular intervals for the construction work, installation of the equipment and to provide the necessary technical systems. These surface sites are likely to be in the canton of Geneva in Switzerland and in the Ain and Haute-Savoie departments in France. Four of the sites are likely to be scientific sites where the collision-point experiments will be installed: sites PA in Ferney-Voltaire, PD in Nangy, PG in Charvonnex and Groisy, and PJ in Vulbens and Dingy-en-Vuache. The four other sites, PB in Choulex and Presinge, PF in Éteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron, PH in Cercier and Marlioz and PL in Challex, are likely to be technical sites.

Given that the main CERN campuses in Meyrin and Prévessin are 40 km away from the furthest point in the FCC, it can be envisaged that an additional centre of activities will be created to work alongside the two main sites. This would enable the efficient allocation of construction and operational tasks. In addition to practical considerations, the successful integration of these sites into their local area requires an analysis of the socio-economic environment and a collaboration that takes this environment into account.

The numbers of personnel required on each site will vary for the different FCC phases such as the design, construction, installation and transition, and the operational phase. This document sets out the assumptions made regarding the numbers of people present on each site during these different phases. It explores the options for the location of this pole, carries out a multicriteria analysis to determine the best location, and estimates the surface area and potential construction cost, making various assumptions about how it might be accommodated.

On the basis of the multicriteria analysis of the six options analysed, the option of site PD in Nangy appears to be the preferred location. Depending on the development strategy of this pole, the number of people associated with it may vary from 70 to 2400.

To understand this document fully, the following points must be borne in mind:

- This document sets out the requirements for a pole and its potential locations. Its purpose is to provide information useful in considering where this pole should be sited. The creation of a pole is not an objective in itself.
- The figures set out in this document are based on those applicable to the current LHC/HL-LHC programmes. The operating method of the FCC has not yet been decided and the figures set out here for the numbers of people present on site are assumptions only.
- The analysis criteria used are those selected initially for the smooth running of the FCC infrastructure. This document serves as basis for consideration by local stakeholders in consultation with each other.
- No decision has yet been made regarding the creation of a pole or its location.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	8
1.1 FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER STUDY	8
1.2 RATIONALE.....	10
1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THIS DOCUMENT.....	11
2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION.....	12
2.1 PHASES OF THE FCC-EE PROJECT.....	12
2.2 SURFACE SITES.....	13
2.3 ACTIVITIES ON THE SURFACE SITES	16
3. ASSUMPTIONS ABOUT THE PERSONNEL AND ACTIVITIES ON THE SITES	17
3.1 DESIGN PHASE.....	17
3.2 CONSTRUCTION, INSTALLATION AND TRANSITION PHASE	18
3.2.1 <i>Activities</i>	18
3.2.2 <i>Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site</i>	19
3.2.3 <i>Personnel living conditions on site</i>	20
3.3 OPERATIONAL, MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADE PHASE	21
3.3.1 <i>Activities</i>	21
3.3.2 <i>Number of people involved in the LHC research programme</i>	22
3.3.3 <i>Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site</i>	24
3.4 SUMMARY OF THE NUMBERS OF PEOPLE PRESENT DURING EACH PHASE.....	27
4. LOCATION HYPOTHESES.....	28
4.1 DEFINITION OF THE ANALYSIS CRITERIA	28
4.1.1 <i>Campus facilities</i>	28
4.1.2 <i>Distances between the sites</i>	29
4.1.3 <i>Establishment of criteria based on proximity to certain key sites and services</i>	31
4.2 PRESENTATION OF THE REGION AND THE OPTIONS	33
4.3 OPTION 1: SITE PG – CHARVONNEX/GROISY	35
4.3.1 <i>Location profile</i>	35
4.3.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	36
4.3.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	38
4.4 OPTION 2: GROISY	39
4.4.1 <i>Location profile</i>	39
4.4.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	40
4.4.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	42
4.5 OPTION 3: CNRS/LAPP ANNECY.....	43
4.5.1 <i>Location profile</i>	43
4.5.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	45
4.5.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	47
4.6 OPTION 4: SITE PJ – DINGY-EN-VUACHE/VULBENS	49
4.6.1 <i>Location profile</i>	49
4.6.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	51
4.6.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	52
4.7 OPTION 5: LA ROCHE-SUR-FORON.....	53
4.7.1 <i>Location profile</i>	53
4.7.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	55
4.7.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	56
4.8 OPTION 6: SITE PD – NANGY	57
4.8.1 <i>Location profile</i>	57
4.8.2 <i>Pole location criteria scores</i>	59
4.8.3 <i>Opportunities and synergies with the local area</i>	59
4.9 SUMMARY.....	61
4.9.1 <i>Recap of the advantages and disadvantages of each option</i>	61

4.9.2	<i>Multicriteria analysis to determine the best location option</i>	63
5.	SURFACE AREA AND COST	65
5.1	ASSUMPTIONS REGARDING THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE POTENTIALLY ASSOCIATED WITH THE POLE	65
5.2	SURFACE AREA AND COST ESTIMATES	68
5.2.1	<i>Surface area estimate</i>	68
5.2.2	<i>Cost estimate</i>	68
6.	CONCLUSION	70
7.	ANNEXES	72
7.1	LIST OF INSTALLATIONS ON THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL SITES	72
7.2	EXPERIMENTS AND TECHNICAL SYSTEMS OF AN ACCELERATOR	74
7.2.1	<i>Scientific site with a detector for an experiment</i>	74
7.2.2	<i>Technical sites with radiofrequency systems</i>	75
7.2.3	<i>Technical sites with cryogenic cooling systems</i>	76
7.2.4	<i>Vacuum systems</i>	77
7.2.5	<i>Cooling and ventilation systems</i>	78
7.2.6	<i>Electrical power supply and distribution</i>	79
7.3	OVERVIEW OF CIVIL ENGINEERING WORKS DURING THE FCC CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION PHASES	80
7.4	NUMBERS OF CIVIL ENGINEERING PERSONNEL DURING THE CONSTRUCTION PHASE	82
7.5	EXPERIENCE GAINED FROM THE LYON-TURIN GRAND CHANTIER TERRITORIAL CONTRACT	83
7.6	LOCATION MATRIX IN KM AND MIN: SITES AND OPTIONS	85
7.7	SWOT ANALYSIS OF LOCATION OPTIONS	86
7.8	LAPP/CNRS PERSONNEL INVOLVED WITH CERN INFRASTRUCTURES AND PROGRAMMES	96
7.9	MULTICRITERIA ANALYSIS AND OPTIONS	97

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: Estimate of the maximum number of civil-engineering contractor personnel present simultaneously on each site during the construction phase.	19
Table 2: Estimated number of personnel present on each site during installation.	20
Table 3: Workforce required for the experiments and technical systems.....	22
Table 4: Personnel present on each scientific and each technical site during the operational phase.	24
Table 5: Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site for each phase.	27
Table 6: Distance and duration matrix for journeys by road between the CERN sites and the FCC sites.....	30
Table 7: Pole location criteria scores for option 1.....	37
Table 8: Pole location criteria scores for option 2.....	41
Table 9: Pole location criteria scores for option 3.....	46
Table 10: Pole location criteria scores for option 4.....	51
Table 11: Pole location criteria scores for option 5.....	55
Table 12: Pole location criteria scores for option 6.....	59
Table 13: Advantages and disadvantages of each option.	61
Table 14: The criteria and their importance weightings.....	63
Table 15: Multicriteria analysis and distance scoring.	64
Table 16: The score calculated for each pole location option.	64
Table 17: Numbers of people present on each site for each phase.	65
Table 18: Surface area estimates for the pole based on the different personnel possibilities.....	68
Table 19: Estimate of the total construction cost of a pole for each personnel possibility considered.	69
Table 20: Summary of personnel numbers, surface areas and costs of the pole for each possibility.....	70
Table 21: List of infrastructures and installations on the surface sites during the operational phase of the FCC-ee.	72
Table 22: Distance and duration matrix for journeys by road between the CERN sites, the FCC sites and the options.	85
Table 23: SWOT analysis of option 1 – PG Charvonnex/Groisy.....	86
Table 24: SWOT analysis of option 2 – Groisy.	88
Table 25: SWOT analysis of option 3 – LAPP/CNRS Annecy.....	90
Table 26: SWOT analysis of option 5 – La Roche-sur-Foron.....	92
Table 27: SWOT analysis of option 6 – PD Nangy.	94
Table 28: Number of people at LAPP working on CERN experiments.....	96
Table 29: Multicriteria analysis, weighting, scores and options.	97

TABLE OF ILLUSTRATIONS

Illustration 1: Overview of the possible siting of the FCC in the region, based on the current working assumption and showing the communes and intercommunal administrative structures directly or indirectly concerned in France (departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie) and Switzerland (canton of Geneva)..... 9

Illustration 2: Different options for accommodating personnel on an activity pole..... 11

Illustration 3: Timetable of the different phases of the FCC-ee (years)..... 12

Illustration 4: Distribution of the scientific and technical sites. 14

Illustration 5: Example of an organisation concept of a scientific site. This image is an illustration only of the key elements of a scientific site. It is not for use as a construction plan. 15

Illustration 6: Places of residence of the people currently involved in the CERN programmes. 23

Illustration 7: CMS control room for approximately 20 people. 25

Illustration 8: ATLAS control room for approximately 20 people..... 25

Illustration 9: Locations of the LHC, the surface sites of the FCC and the motorway network..... 29

Illustration 10: Potential options for the location of the pole. 34

Illustration 11: Location of site option 1 at Charvonnex and facilities in the surrounding area..... 35

Illustration 12: Location of site option 2 at Groisy and facilities in the surrounding area. 39

Illustration 13: Location of site option 3 at Annecy and facilities in the surrounding area..... 43

Illustration 14: Aerial view of the LAPP/CNRS site..... 45

Illustration 15: Location of site option 4 at Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens and facilities in the surrounding area. 50

Illustration 16: Location of site option 6 at La Roche-sur-Foron and facilities in the surrounding area..... 54

Illustration 17: Location of site option 5 at Nangy and facilities in the surrounding area. 58

Illustration 18: Different possibilities for accommodating FCC personnel on the pole. 66

Illustration 19: Possibilities for accommodating FCC personnel on the pole (approximate figures)..... 67

Illustration 20: Locations and ranking of the options..... 71

Illustration 21: The CMS experiment at the LHC. 74

Illustration 22: One of the modules containing the accelerating cavities for the LHC..... 75

Illustration 23: Cryogenic installation at point 5 of the mounting hall of the CMS experiment. 76

Illustration 24: The vacuum at the LHC..... 77

Illustration 25: Cooling and ventilation..... 78

Illustration 26: Electrical transformer for the LHC. 79

Illustration 27: Numbers of personnel present simultaneously on each site during each year of the construction phase..... 82

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER STUDY

The purpose of the feasibility study of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) is to develop a concept for a new research infrastructure to accommodate the next generation of higher-performance particle colliders designed to extend the research currently being carried out at CERN once the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) research programme concludes in around 2040.

The objective of the FCC programme is to extend the boundaries of the beam intensity and the energy of the particle colliders with a view to conducting research in new physics. Under the programme, two particle colliders will be installed and operated in succession in a new underground installation with a circumference of approximately 91 km. This scientific research programme using these two machines is likely to last until the end of the 21st century. The working assumption is to have a first operational phase with an electron-positron collider (FCC-ee) up to 2057, followed by a second operational phase with a hadron collider (FCC-hh). An international collaboration bringing together more than 150 universities, research institutes and industrial partners from all over the world is working on developing the concepts relating to two circular colliders, new detectors for the experiments installed at the collision points, and the technical infrastructures required to operate these installations. It is also working on drawing up cost estimates, worldwide implementation scenarios and appropriate governance structures.

The report summarising the constraints and opportunities regarding the siting of the FCC ¹ (Gutleber et al., 2023) states that eight access sites positioned at regular intervals are planned for the construction work, the installation of the equipment and to provide the necessary technical systems, each with a surface area of between four and seven hectares approximately. Based on CERN's experience and an inventory of its existing assets, approximately 80% of this surface area would be taken up by the buildings and technical installations. The rest would be used for site logistics and to ensure that the sites are appropriately integrated into their environmental, landscape and urban contexts.

This underground infrastructure would be located in an area spanning the Swiss/French border. The tunnel would run underneath Lake Geneva and the Arve and Rhône rivers. One technical site² would be located in Switzerland, one technical and one scientific site³ would be located in the Ain department in France, and the five remaining sites (three scientific and two technical sites) would be located in the Haute-Savoie department in France (see Illustration 1). The headquarters of CERN in Meyrin (Switzerland) would remain operational. The CERN site in Prévessin (France) would be used to operate the injector complex for the FCC.

¹ Gutleber et al., 2023, Synthèse des contraintes et opportunités d'implantation du Futur Collisionneur Circulaire (FCC), <https://zenodo.org/record/7614421>.

² Technical sites: used solely for the technical installations required for the smooth operation of the machine. Scientific sites: used solely to conduct the experiments.

³ In addition to the current CERN sites.

Illustration 1: Overview of the possible siting of the FCC in the region, based on the current working assumption and showing the communes and intercommunal administrative structures directly or indirectly concerned in France (departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie) and Switzerland (canton of Geneva).

The locations of the surface sites of the technical installations have been optimised using the “avoid-reduce-compensate” principle (the ERC sequence in article R122-5 of the French Environment Code⁴), taking into account constraints arising from the design of the particle collider, local development considerations identified at this stage (particularly with regard to urban development, nature and agriculture), and numerous other aspects in order to limit its impact while still creating a world-class scientific installation. This study has adopted the ERC approach to balance the objectives of scientific excellence with compatibility at local level and the risks related to the implementation of the project.

⁴ https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000043743342

1.2 RATIONALE

To design a new research infrastructure using circular particle colliders on a large scale located in a cross-border region taking in a mix of urban and rural areas and characterised by a mountainous topography that imposes constraints in terms of road and rail infrastructures, it is necessary to define the way in which the construction and operation of such an infrastructure must be allocated.

Site PA of the FCC at Ferney-Voltaire and the main CERN campuses in Meyrin and Prévessin are located at the furthest point from site PG of the FCC 40 km away, which raises the question of whether any additional activity pole should be created in the southern or south-eastern part of the FCC. In addition to the practical considerations, there is also the matter of ensuring better integration into the local area, which can only be achieved by taking into account the socio-economic environment of that area and adapting to it as closely as possible.

Thus, the considerations providing the rationale for this study are as follows:

- The broad **geographical extent** of this research infrastructure;
- the **possibility of relieving pressure on CERN's existing sites**, where space is already at a premium;
- the **limitations** in terms of **road and rail transport** infrastructures;
- the **border** between two countries, one of which is not a member of the European Union;
- the **number of people contributing** to the scientific programme, at installations some distance apart;
- the opportunity to **allocate the activities of construction, installation, maintenance and repair**;
- changes in society with respect to **mobility**;
- changes in society in terms of **work and lifestyle habits**;
- a balanced **integration into the local area**;
- **regional development of the local area**;
- **tourism development**;
- **planning for the socio-economic repercussions**, for example by providing local training opportunities;
- **economic development**.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THIS DOCUMENT

The objective of this document is to set out the requirements of an activity site complementary to CERN’s existing sites, which we shall call a “pole”.

A collider such as the FCC requires the services of various teams specialising in different technical systems and also involves scientific collaborations taking place on the scientific sites (the experiments) (see Annex 7.2 for more details). An additional pole could accommodate scientists and engineers working in a scientific collaboration and also specialist or multidisciplinary teams working on the different technical systems required for the design, construction, installation and operation of the FCC at the different surface sites. For example, the team responsible for the radiofrequency systems on a given pole could take on responsibility for all of the FCC’s radiofrequency systems regardless of their location; a team specialising in vacuum systems could look after the vacuum systems in certain sectors of the FCC determined by the locations of the surface sites; a multidisciplinary team could be responsible for different technologies in a given sector; a scientific collaboration located on a given pole could run one or two experiments on a specific FCC site. These examples are just possible scenarios. There are many different options, which could be combined as appropriate (see Illustration 2⁵).

Illustration 2: Different options for accommodating personnel on an activity pole.

The purpose of this document is to examine options for the allocation of personnel and of the requirements of the FCC during the different phases concerned, with sites spaced around the collider, and to provide a vision for its sustainable operation in the long term, with one or more science, technology and innovation hubs.

This document focuses on developing a new complementary pole working in cooperation with CERN’s main sites at Meyrin in Switzerland and Prévessin in France. It examines the option of having a single pole accommodating the different teams and also the option of having several poles for the different requirements.

⁵ A sector refers to a part of the FCC located between two access sites.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

2.1 PHASES OF THE FCC-EE PROJECT

The construction, installation, commissioning, operation, maintenance and continuous improvement of a particle collider require both a suitable technical, science and technology installation and multidisciplinary personnel carrying out a variety of activities. Illustration 3 shows the time required, in years, to complete these different phases of the first iteration of the FCC: the FCC-ee. Subsequently, the FCC-hh will run until the end of the century.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35
Conception										Exploitation																								
Construction et installation										Z			W		H		Amélioration		TT															

Illustration 3: Timetable of the different phases of the FCC-ee (years)

The main activities that will take place during these different phases are listed below:

- **Design:** bringing together scientists, engineers and contractors to design the technical systems and infrastructures. The design activities of the various systems and sub-systems overlap with the construction and installation phases of other infrastructures such as the underground work and the construction of the technical infrastructures of the surface sites (over a period of approximately 20 years).
- **Construction:** working with contractors and research partners to develop and assemble the equipment; supervising the construction work on the different sites; constructing the underground infrastructure and associated equipment and constructing the surface sites (over a period of approximately 10 years, overlapping with the design phase, and then in stages to upgrade the collider and experiments).
- **Installation and transition to operation:** checking and testing the equipment to be installed; assembling some sub-systems in situ; installing the equipment and detectors for the experiments; commissioning the systems; validating correct functioning. (Approximately 4 years, overlapping with and extending slightly beyond the construction phase.)
- **Operation:** driving the accelerators and their sub-systems on the scientific and technical sites; operating the detectors on the scientific sites; collecting data; working with scientists all over the world to analyse the data collected and carry out research in physics; monitoring the equipment and ensuring its smooth and safe operation; maintaining the surface sites and underground installations (over a period of approximately 15 years).
- **Technical maintenance and repairs:** carrying out regular technical maintenance work on the equipment and infrastructures; responding within a reasonable time in the event of a fault and scheduling and carrying out the necessary repair work (over a period of 15 years during the operational phase).
- **Upgrading:** scheduling and implementing continuous improvements to the efficiency and performance of the accelerators and detectors; working with communities of scientists, engineers and contractors all over the world to develop the upgrades; placing contracts for the developments; supervising, installing and commissioning the upgrades. (Improvements are scheduled throughout the operational period but are mainly implemented during the long shutdown lasting one year.)

2.2 SURFACE SITES

To maintain and operate the infrastructure, surface sites are required. The locations of these surface sites are shown in Illustration 1: Overview of the possible siting of the FCC in the region, based on the current working assumption and showing the communes and intercommunal administrative structures directly or indirectly concerned in France (departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie) and Switzerland (canton of Geneva). in section 1.1: Overview of the possible siting of the FCC in the region, based on the current working assumption and showing the communes and intercommunal administrative structures directly or indirectly concerned in France (departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie) and Switzerland (canton of Geneva).

The surface sites are used for:

- constructing the shafts, tunnels and caverns underground;
- installing the particle accelerators;
- assembling and installing the detectors used in the experiments;
- supplying the machine with resources (electricity, cooling water, cold air);
- cooling equipment in the tunnel: the acceleration systems (such as the radiofrequency acceleration systems and superconducting magnets) by means of cryogenic refrigeration installations on the surface; and the electromagnets, using industrial water-based cooling systems;
- collecting and analysing the data generated by the experiments in specialised computing centres;
- accessing the underground installations.

The eight surface sites are divided into two categories: scientific sites and technical sites (see Illustration 4; the circles shown do not represent the surface areas of these sites **Error! Reference source not found.**).

The FCC can host up to four experiments, which will be located at the following sites:

1. PA at Ferney-Voltaire;
2. PG at Groisy and Charvonnex;
3. PD at Nangy; and
4. PJ at Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens.

The following sites:

1. PB at Presinge and Choulex;
2. PF at Éteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron;
3. PH at Cercier and Marlioz; and
4. PL at Challex

will be technical sites.

Illustration 4: Distribution of the scientific and technical sites.

A scientific site differs from a technical site in that it features additional facilities such as infrastructures for the assembly, testing and installation of the detector used in the experiment, a control room to run the experiment, meeting rooms, offices, workshops and a computing centre. The sites include several buildings. The installations will differ depending on the phase the FCC.

Table 21 in Annex 7.1 lists the different site-specific infrastructures and installations that are likely to be present on the scientific and technical sites during the operational phase. These infrastructures are not common to all sites; some may be found on some sites and not on others.

The footprint of a scientific site is six to seven hectares, approximately four of which are taken up by constructions. The footprint of a technical site is four to seven hectares, with approximately three hectares being taken up by constructions, depending on the equipment present. Open spaces are required for the transportation, unloading and temporary storage of equipment on the surface during the construction, installation and upgrade phases and to ensure the sites are appropriately integrated into the landscape.

During the construction of the underground infrastructures, the surface sites will also be used for the sorting, processing and temporary storage of the excavated materials and for the assembly of equipment during installation.

Illustration 5: Example of an organisation concept of a scientific site. shows an example of an organisation concept of a scientific site.

Illustration 5: Example of an organisation concept of a scientific site. This image is an illustration only of the key elements of a scientific site. It is not for use as a construction plan.

2.3 ACTIVITIES ON THE SURFACE SITES

Many activities take place on the surface sites. Generally, the following equipment is found there:

- the four experiments with the detectors, on the scientific sites where the particle beams cross (PA, PG, PD, PJ);
- the radiofrequency systems (PH, PL);
- the cryogenic cooling systems;
- the vacuum systems;
- the cooling and ventilation systems;
- the electrical power supply and power distribution network.

Annex 7.12 explains in more detail how the experiments and systems work.

The following sections provide information about the number of people required to operate these systems, whether these people need to remain on site, and how close to the site they must be to operate these systems properly during each phase.

3. ASSUMPTIONS ABOUT THE PERSONNEL AND ACTIVITIES ON THE SITES

3.1 DESIGN PHASE

The design phase takes place alongside the day-to-day activities of the personnel working at CERN and around the world. For this phase it is not necessary for the personnel to travel to the area where the FCC will be constructed. During the design phase there will not necessarily be any requirements for the pole. The personnel will work on the CERN campuses in Meyrin and Prévessin and in CERN's different existing laboratories. It is during this phase that the design of the accelerator, detectors, technical systems and surface sites will be determined.

3.2 CONSTRUCTION, INSTALLATION AND TRANSITION PHASE

3.2.1 Activities

The civil-engineering work will take place on each of the eight surface sites and on the existing CERN site in Prévessin. It will take approximately ten years to complete all of the underground and surface civil-engineering work.

3.2.1.1 Construction activities

The construction activities listed below will need to be carried out on each site.

- Adaptation or construction of access roads to the construction sites.
- Preparation of the construction sites, including construction of temporary offices and workshops and provision of the resources required to complete the civil-engineering work.
- Installations for sorting and processing the spoil and for temporary storage before recycling of the excavated materials (soil, brick, insulating materials, concrete, etc.).
- Construction of one shaft on the technical sites PB, PF, PH and PL and of two shafts on the experimental sites PA, PD, PG and PJ.
- Excavation of the underground tunnels and caverns located near the shafts.
- Installation of a tunnel boring machine (TBM) on six to eight sites to begin the excavation work.
- Excavation of the approximately 11 km of tunnel section for each of the eight sectors of the tunnel.
- Disassembly of the TBM via the adjacent site.
- Installation of the floor and drainage network in the tunnel.
- Construction of the reinforced concrete linings in all tunnels, caverns and shafts.
- Installation of all steel structures, in particular in the large caverns.
- Painting of all underground structures.
- Installation of the modules for the lifts and staircases.
- Completion of the surface buildings and of the other surface building work.
- Removal of temporary civil-engineering structures.

More detailed information about the civil-engineering work is provided in Annex 7.3.

Once the civil-engineering work has been completed on a site, the personnel responsible for the installations and technical systems of the accelerator and the personnel working in the collaborations will need to install these elements to get the machine up and running.

3.2.1.2 Installation and transition activities

The installation and transition phase will consist of the following:

- Fitting out of the surface sites.
- Fitting out of the injector in Prévessin.
- Installation of the equipment in the underground structures.
- Start up of the machine.

3.2.2 Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site

3.2.2.1 Number of people present during construction

During this period, the estimated number of people present varies greatly by site and by year. On some sites there may be as many as 300 people present at the same time ⁶ (see Table 1). For more details, see the bar chart in Annex 7.4, which summarises the numbers of personnel present at the same time on each site in the different years concerned.

Table 1: Estimate of the maximum number of civil-engineering contractor personnel present simultaneously on each site during the construction phase.

Site	Workforce
PA	≈ 100
PB	≈ 130
PD	≈ 290
PF	≈ 70
PG	≈ 260
PH	≈ 70
PJ	≈ 260
PL	≈ 130
Prévessin	≈ 130
Total	≈ 1440

3.2.2.2 Number of people present during installation

During the installation phase it is first and foremost safety criteria that determine the number of people able to be on site. An emergency evacuation analysis has determined the maximum number of people permitted to work underground at the same time in a given tunnel sector. One sector, the section of tunnel between two sites, is approximately 11 330 m long. People working underground at a site must be spread evenly along the site. If an incident occurs at a site, for example site PB, half of the workforce (having descended at site PA) and the other half (having descended at site PB) will thus be able to evacuate via site PA. Calculated at two to three people per vehicle, between 170 and 260 people are therefore permitted to be present in a single tunnel sector at the same time. This means that approximately 170 to 260 people (plus a small additional number of technicians)

⁶ The figures shown, indicating up to approximately 300 people, represent the number of workers present on the site at the same time. This estimate includes underground operators, for whom the actual number of people present at any given time will generally vary at somewhere between 35 and 50% of the total because of the shift-work pattern. The total number of people present on a daily basis may be as many as 500.

are permitted to work at a site at the same time. Consequently, during the installation and upgrade phases, it can be expected that fewer than 300 people will be on each site.

The number of people present each year on each site varies less during the installation phase than it does during construction phase (see Table 2).

Table 2: Estimated number of personnel present on each site during installation.

Site	Workforce
4 x Scientific	200 to 300
4 x Technical	≈ 100
Total	≈ 1600

3.2.3 Personnel living conditions on site

The surface sites have different requirements for premises, offices, workshops and personnel accommodation during the different phases of the project. Temporary offices and workshops will be installed locally on the construction sites. These will be removed once the civil-engineering work is complete.

The type of accommodation provided for the workforce during the construction phase will depend on the local situation. If there is enough accommodation within a reasonable distance from the worksite, contractors will favour this solution. If this is not the case, the contractor will have to plan for the construction of a contractor’s base near the worksite for its workforce. It is worth noting that for some previous major civil-engineering projects for CERN, the land on which the contractor’s base has been constructed has been provided by the local municipal council in exchange for the use of the buildings by the council once the civil-engineering work has been completed.

Although contractors do not need to have an installation for visitors, CERN envisages providing an installation for use by visitors to the surface sites during the construction phase. As the TELT (Lyon-Turin tunnel) project has successfully demonstrated, a large construction project like the FCC is a major attraction and making it accessible to visitors is a good way of raising awareness of the project among the public.

Generally, for a civil-engineering project such as the FCC, LHC or LEP⁷, the directors and management staff involved work on the project for several years. Consequently, some of them may move to the area with their families and will need local facilities such as schools, healthcare services (doctors and dentists), restaurants/cafés and accommodation.

The workers, many of whom will be coming from far away, will probably not be accompanied by their families; it is assumed that they will return home when they can. This is of course not a set rule because it will depend greatly on which contractors are involved in the construction work. It might be possible to re-use the installations erected and used during the construction phase for the pole. However, given that these installations are generally temporary, this has not been the practice in the past. It is therefore worth giving some thought to this possibility in advance.

In this context, it may be appropriate to conclude a “Grand Chantier” territorial contract. Annex 7.5 presents the actions implemented under the Lyon-Turin Grand Chantier territorial contract and the outcome after three years.

⁷ The collider that preceded the current LHC

3.3 OPERATIONAL, MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADE PHASE

3.3.1 Activities

The design, construction and infrastructure-installation phases are followed by the operational phase. This phase generally lasts for eight months at a time, followed by four months of maintenance and repair work. The operational phase comprises five parts: Z, W, H, upgrade, and tt. Z, W, H and tt are operational modes defined in the scientific programme. On the other hand, the upgrade period is a scheduled year-long shutdown during which additional items of equipment are installed to enhance the collider's performance. This period is comparable with the installation phase in terms of the number of people present.

To ensure that the accelerator functions as it should, personnel are required to operate technical installations specific to a particular machine and to run the detector experiments in worldwide collaborations.

The technical systems include the superconducting radiofrequency systems that accelerate the particles, which are key systems. Two FCC-ee sites will accommodate such systems: PL (Challex, France) and PH (Cercier and Marlioz, France). It is therefore important to understand how these systems work and to estimate the number of people required on site since this information will influence the location of the potential pole (see Box 1).

Box 1: Operation of the radiofrequency systems.

The CERN radiofrequency systems during the operational phase:

During the operational phase, no personnel is required to be on site. If an intervention becomes necessary, the control room informs the person in charge of the system, who takes approximately one hour to reach the site. If there is an electrical fault, technicians are generally on site within around 30 minutes. The systems are generally managed from a gallery containing the amplifiers (klystrons) and all the electronic equipment. When the accelerator is operating, interventions are always made on the surface and from the control rooms. In the event of an emergency and when there is no alternative but to access the machine, it is necessary to schedule a shutdown so that the machine can be accessed.

The Jefferson Lab radiofrequency systems during the operational phase:

During operation, most personnel work remotely. Systems specialists are rarely called upon to intervene during this period. **If the event of a fault, they can generally detect it, diagnose it and intervene remotely.** **There is no requirement for personnel to be on site permanently.** If an intervention is required, technicians are generally on site within around 30 minutes.

As far as the other technical systems are concerned, only a small number of technicians are required on site permanently to keep them operational. **Generally, these technicians work on site as and when needed.** In 20 years' time, in around 2045 when operation of the infrastructure will begin, it is possible that the presence of technicians will be even less necessary given the increasing trend towards automation and the possibility of managing and repairing the systems remotely. It is worth noting that, for now, we do not know exactly how these systems will be operated. On the other hand, **during the other phases, including the installation, maintenance and upgrade phases, personnel will have to be present on site.**

3.3.2 Number of people involved in the LHC research programme

Before considering the number of people present on each site, it is helpful to look at how the current research programme is structured (Table 3).

All of the personnel involved in the LHC research programme can be divided into two main categories:

- the experiment personnel taking part in the international collaborations related to the scientific sites;
- the personnel working on the technical systems and technical infrastructures.

Table 3: Workforce required for the experiments and technical systems.

	Workforce
Total for the four experiments⁸	≈ 13 000
<i>For one main experiment</i>	≈ 5000
<i>For one complementary experiment</i>	≈ 1500
Of whom resident in the region	≈ 5000
Technical systems	≈ 2100
Of whom resident in the region	≈ 1800

The figures shown in Table 3 are taken from the personnel statistics of CERN'S Human Resources Department⁹ and are based on the experiment at the Laboratory. Some 2000 other members of the personnel take part in research programmes in other fields (including international relations, human resources and finance) and do not necessarily need to be physically close to the infrastructure. Most of them work on the CERN campuses in Meyrin and Prévessin. In all, some 16 000 people are registered at CERN, **around 9000 of whom are resident in the region. These figures are assumed for the FCC programme, based on the figures for the LHC research programme. The operational model for the FCC has not yet been decided.**

The number shown for one main experiment corresponds to the workforce that may be present on two scientific sites. The number shown for one complementary experiment corresponds to the workforce that may be present on two additional scientific sites. Thus, the number of personnel working on the experiments, approximately 13 000, is the sum of the personnel working on the two large experiments and the two smaller experiments. **As yet, the locations of the future main experiments have not been decided (PA/PG or PD/PJ).**

The experiments are worldwide collaborations. This means that the majority of the people involved (around 60%) are located at their laboratories elsewhere in the world. On the other hand, most of the people who are not part of the international collaboration but who work for CERN are located on the CERN sites and are therefore resident in the region. A number of the people taking part in the worldwide collaboration come to work at CERN for a few weeks and in some cases for up to six months. These people are not resident in the region but because

⁸ two main experiments and two complementary experiments

⁹ <https://cds.cern.ch/collection/CERN%20Annual%20Personnel%20Statistics?ln=fr>

they are present at CERN they are added to the number of people present over the year. Given that they are replaced during the year by other visiting collaborators, this number can be included in the total of people resident all year round. **Consequently, 55% of this workforce, totalling some 9000 people (Alix & Gutleber, 2023), can be regarded as resident in the region,** generally in the cantons of Geneva and Vaud and the departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie.

For information purposes, Illustration 6 shows the locations of the places of residence of the people who currently work for the CERN programmes. This illustration shows that these places of residence are scattered around the region.

Illustration 6: Places of residence of the people currently involved in the CERN programmes.

It is difficult to foresee where a person taking part in the FCC programme might choose to live. This decision depends on several factors such as the type of job, the likely location of the workplace, any requirement to commute, family situation, financial situation and also personal preference. It is apparent that, in the case of the LHC programme, the choice of commune of residence is determined by the quality of the transport provision between the place of residence and the place of work. As we can see, the places of residence are spread around the Ain and Haute-Savoie departments in France and the cantons of Geneva and Vaud in Switzerland. There is a high concentration of places of residence in Saint-Genis-Pouilly (France) and in Geneva (Switzerland) around the Meyrin site, given that many scientists are dependent on good public transport connections between their place of residence and their place of work. The fact that some personnel have chosen to live near the D884 and D984 roads in France is determined by the fact that these people wish to live in a rural area while remaining well connected. This complicates the task of identifying a preferred location for an additional activity campus. However, good public transport connections (bus, tram, train) will certainly be a key factor.

We have seen that a scientific research programme requires a very diverse range of people, some resident and others not. It is now helpful to make a more detailed assessment of the number of people required to come and work at the sites, both on the surface and underground.

3.3.3 Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site

Since the sites in Meyrin and Prévessin are CERN’s main sites, most of the personnel are likely to work at these two sites in the future, as is the case currently. On the other hand, to reduce commuting distances, for convenience and to maintain connections with some of the surface sites (and depending on the phase of the FCC), it is probable that some of these people will be present on the FCC sites.

Table 5 provides **an estimate of the numbers of personnel required on the scientific and technical sites during the different operating periods of the machine. These figures are based on those for the LHC programme.** Note that in the case of the LHC the long shutdowns are more frequent and last for longer (a two-year shutdown approximately every three years). By contrast, for the FCC-ee programme there will be just one long shutdown lasting for one year. The figures for the long shutdown for the upgrade are the same as those for the installation phase.

Table 4: Personnel present on each scientific and each technical site during the operational phase.

	Operation	Annual maintenance	Long shutdown for upgrade
Period	8 months of each year	4 months of each year	1 year, once during the entire programme duration
Personnel on one scientific site	4 to 8 team members and 12 to 16 technicians	100 technicians	200 to 300 technicians
Personnel on one technical site	0 to 9 technicians	15 to 30 technicians	100 technicians

The figures for team members are based on the example of the figures for the control room of the CMS experiment, for which the number of desks and the categories of sub-detectors are shown in Illustration 7 below. During the operational phase, most of these desks are not used. In Illustration 7, only the desks outlined must be occupied. The control room of the ATLAS experiment provides another example. In Illustration 8, the desks outlined must be occupied while the accelerator is running. These rooms can accommodate around 20 people but it is seldom that all desks are occupied. Most of the time only four to eight people (making up one team) are required. On the technical sites, it is likely that a maximum of approximately 10 people will be on site at all times, and this figure could be less if developments in remote monitoring continue. Furthermore, these people may arrive on site to complete their tasks and then return to their offices providing that these are reasonably close to the site. During the other periods, particularly the annual maintenance, the technicians¹⁰ must be present on site at all times to work on the installations.

¹⁰ Technicians and engineers

Illustration 7: CMS control room for approximately 20 people.

Illustration 8: ATLAS control room for approximately 20 people.

These are the people who are required to be present on site throughout the different phases. **Members of the personnel involved in the collaboration therefore do not necessarily need to be present on site. They can work remotely** from their home laboratory, from where they live, or from CERN'S Meyrin and Prévessin sites. The same applies to the personnel working on the technical systems, who are often located at CERN.

This situation may change in the next 20 years. We do not yet have a clear idea of the technologies that will be used in the future or of the role and importance of automation in the smooth running of the machine.

3.4 SUMMARY OF THE NUMBERS OF PEOPLE PRESENT DURING EACH PHASE

Table 5 summarises the estimates of the numbers of people expected to be on each site throughout the FCC-ee programme, including during the construction phase, based on the figures for the LHC programme.

Table 5: Assumptions regarding the numbers of people present on each site for each phase.

	Construction	Installation	Operation	Annual maintenance	Long shutdown for upgrade
Period	10 years	5 years (overlaps with the construction phase)	8 months of each year	4 months of each year	1 year, once during the entire programme duration
Personnel on one scientific site	40 to 300 workers	200 to 300 technicians	4 to 8 team members 12 to 16 technicians	100 technicians	200 to 300 technicians
Personnel on one technical site	20 to 130 workers	100 technicians	0 to 9 technicians	15 to 30 technicians	100 technicians

4. LOCATION HYPOTHESES

4.1 DEFINITION OF THE ANALYSIS CRITERIA

4.1.1 Campus facilities

Different services and facilities are present on the CERN campuses in Meyrin and Prévessin. These may also be necessary, to varying degrees, at an additional pole, depending on its location and layout.

The following services and facilities are essential:

- offices;
- meeting rooms and general purpose rooms;
- cafeteria;
- emergency services.

The following services and facilities are less important and more dependent on the size of the pole:

- conference rooms;
- restaurant;
- accommodation;
- bank;
- small retail outlets (e.g. newsagent, convenience store);
- post office;
- visitor centre with information about the scientific sites with a mini-restaurant and café, souvenir shop, access for visitors, exhibitions;
- training and education centre;
- technical and computer labs;
- transport facilities (shuttle bus, cars, bicycles, scooters, etc.);
- day nursery.

A pole accommodating the people working on the FCC programme will need to offer a large number of services. These services may be provided as an integral part of the pole or may be provided by existing facilities located near the pole with which a close working relationship can be built.

Besides the work carried out in the offices, many activities contributing to campus life are necessary for the smooth functioning of an international collaboration and a research programme.

4.1.2 Distances between the sites

The distances between the sites, as indicated by Illustration 9: Locations of the LHC, the surface sites of the FCC and the motorway network., is the main reason why the location of an additional pole must be given careful consideration.

Illustration 9: Locations of the LHC, the surface sites of the FCC and the motorway network.

Given that the Meyrin and Préveessin sites are located to the north-west of the FCC infrastructure, providing easy access to sites PA, PL, PJ and potentially PD, it would seem appropriate to locate any new pole further south. The location of the technical site PB in Presinge/Choulex, Switzerland, presents a challenge in terms of accessibility. However, this site will not house systems requiring intensive maintenance. On the other hand, it is important that site PH in Cercier/Marlioz, which will host a large number of radiofrequency systems, is made more accessible by this potential pole. For this reason it would be preferable to locate such a pole near one of the experiment sites (PD, PG or PJ in Haute-Savoie), where most of the scientists belonging to the collaboration working on that experiment could potentially be based.

No decision has yet been made about how expertise and activities will be divided up between the different campuses. This decision will be informed by a more advanced technical design of the research infrastructure and a more precise inventory of the workforce, and types of personnel required. At this stage, it is possible to analyse the distances between the FCC sites and CERN’s existing installations to gain a clearer idea of the locations that might benefit from an additional pole.

The colours shown in Table 6 indicate the distances by road between the sites, along with the corresponding journey times:

- In **green**, up to 29 minutes.
- In **orange**, between 30 and 40 minutes.
- In **red**, more than 40 minutes.

Table 6: Distance and duration matrix for journeys by road between the CERN sites and the FCC sites.

	CERN Meyrin	CERN Prévessin	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL
CERN Meyrin	0	4.0 km 7 min	4.6 km 10 min	17.1 km 40 min	37.3 km 32 min	49.0 km 40 min	39.9 km 40 min	35.3 km 35 min	29.3 km 27 min	13.2 km 12 min
CERN Prévessin	4.0 km 7 min	0	3.6 km 5 min	21.5 km 35 min	40.9 km 35 min	52.2 km 41 min	43.5 km 41 min	38.6 km 36 min	30.3 km 26 min	14.2 km 13 min
PA	4.6 km 10 min	3.6 km 5 min	0	18.6 km 40 min	38.0 km 34 min	49.3 km 40 min	40.6 km 43 min	35.8 km 40 min	34.2 km 35 min	18.2 km 21 min
PB	17.1 km 40 min	21.5 km 35 min	18.6 km 40 min	0	14.6 km 18 min	26.2 km 27 min	39.8 km 38 min	37.9 km 37 min	34.4 km 36 min	32.5 km 45 min
PD	37.3 km 32 min	40.9 km 35 min	38 km 34 min	14.6 km 18 min	0	14.5 km 12 min	28.2 km 24 min	40.3 km 31 min	38.4 km 34 min	41.2 km 42 min
PF	49.0 km 40 min	52.2 km 41 min	49.3 km 40 min	26.2 km 27 min	14.5 km 12 min	0	13.2 km 12 min	35.6 km 30 min	50.1 km 41 min	52.7 km 47 min
PG	39.9 km 40 min	43.5 km 41 min	40.6 km 43 min	39.8 km 38 min	28.2 km 24 min	13.2 km 12 min	0	17.7 km 22 min	41.3 km 39 min	43.9 km 45 min
PH	35.3 km 35 min	38.6 km 36 min	35.8 km 40 min	37.9 km 37 min	40.3 km 31 min	35.6 km 30 min	17.7 km 22 min	0	15.2 km 21 min	38.0 km 45 min
PJ	29.3 km 27 min	30.3 km 26 min	34.2 km 35 min	34.4 km 36 min	38.4 km 34 min	50.1 km 41 min	41.3 km 39 min	15.2 km 21 min	0	21.1 km 20 min
PL	13.2 km 12 min	14.2 km 13 min	18.2 km 21 min	32.5 km 45 min	41.2 km 42 min	52.7 km 47 min	43.9 km 45 min	38.0 km 45 min	21.1 km 20 min	0

An additional pole could facilitate the operation of the FCC, in particular if it served sites PB (Presinge/Choulex, Switzerland), PF (Étaux/La Roche-sur-Foron, France), PG (Charvonnex/Groisy, France) and PH (Cercier/Marlioz, France).

Broadly speaking, sites PA (Ferney-Voltaire, France), PD (Nangy, France), PJ (Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens, France) and PL (Challex, France) are easily accessible from CERN's existing sites.

By way of comparison, **scientific site P5 of the LHC (the CMS experiment) is between 13 and 15 km by road from CERN**, a journey that takes approximately **20 minutes by car**. Technical sites P4 (Echenevex) and P6 (Versonnex) are comparable distances away.

Sites PB, PF, PG and PH are the furthest from CERN in its current arrangement.

For these least accessible sites, the preferred scientific sites as possible locations for a pole are as follows:

- **for PB: PD** (accessibility from PD is likely to be further improved by the A40 link road project – Carrefour des Chasseurs junction);
- **for PF: PD or PG;**
- **for PG: PG or PD;**
- **for PH: PG or PJ.**

It is apparent that **a pole at site PD could facilitate services for sites PB, PF and PG. PH is more easily accessible from sites PJ and PG.** Given the road connections, a distribution of skills between these two scientific sites could be envisaged. Improvements to public transport could influence the choice of location.

Other location criteria need to be considered besides the distances between the existing CERN sites and the FCC sites.

4.1.3 Establishment of criteria based on proximity to certain key sites and services

The criteria based on proximity to certain sites and services are defined by their importance on a scale of 1 to 5 (with 1 being optional and 5 being necessary).

- Proximity to technical site PH at Cercier/Marlioz As mentioned in section 3.3.1, this site will host the radiofrequency system for the FCC-ee collider. This particle accelerator system is a key system. Ideally, an operations pole should be located less than a 30-minute drive from here, which roughly equates to the distance from La Roche-sur-Foron, Charvonnex and Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens.
Importance: 5
- Proximity to scientific site PG at Charvonnex/Groisy The operations pole would have direct links with site PG. The main purpose of the pole is to accommodate the people whose work is connected with this site. It is therefore a requirement that the pole and the site are no more than 20 minutes apart. However, this scientific site will accommodate all of the equipment required to run and maintain the experiment. It is likely that the people working on this site will live reasonably close to the site and travel directly to the site from their homes.
Importance: 4
- Adequate proximity to the other sites Assuming that the technical and scientific sites are split geographically, with half being served by the existing CERN campus and the other half by an additional pole, we consider that the ideal distance between the pole and sites PB, PD, PF, PG and PH would be approximately 20 minutes.
Importance: 4

- Proximity to the emergency services It is essential that the emergency services are able to provide any necessary assistance. Depending on the partnership arrangement, it will be important that emergency services are available nearby and able to reach the site in less than 10 minutes by road. If the emergency services are too far away, one possibility would be to have a emergency response sub-facility on each site.
Importance: 4
- Proximity to public transport It would be useful for site personnel to be able to use public transport to travel to the surrounding sites and services.
Importance: 3
- Proximity to local shops and services It would be useful for site personnel to have access to local shops and services for their daily requirements. These would include for example restaurants and cafés, accommodation for team members on short-term temporary postings, and day-to-day amenities such as a bank and grocery store. These services could be located either on the site itself or in the surrounding area (through partnerships). Ideally, these should be located with a 15-minute radius by car and 10 minutes by bicycle or public transport (not including public transport waiting times).
Importance: 3
- Proximity to conference halls/amphitheatres CERN's scientific collaborators frequently organise conferences, which are currently held at CERN, Geneva International Conference Centre or other venues. Having halls nearby that are capable of hosting conferences helps to cultivate the idea of research and science for all. Maximum distance: 30 minutes.
Importance: 1
- Proximity to universities For the purposes of possible collaboration with training and educational establishments, it may be useful to have universities in the vicinity. This could help give credence to the idea of a higher education pole. Types of universities: research, physics, administration and technical institutes.
Importance: 1
- Proximity to companies Since contracts are awarded on the basis of calls for tenders, contractors can be located in different places. It is therefore not necessary to have contractors based nearby, except if one of the objectives is to create a technology park for innovative businesses.
Importance: 1

These criteria are designed to support the multicriteria analysis set out below, the results of which are discussed in section 4.9.2.

These criteria and their relative importance have been selected with the smooth operation of the FCC programme in mind. Local stakeholders may have different expectations and wishes.

4.2 PRESENTATION OF THE REGION AND THE OPTIONS

The region under consideration includes part of two countries, France and Switzerland, two French departments and one Swiss canton, some nine EPCIs (Public Intercommunal Cooperation Establishments) and around 40 communes. This area also includes part of Lake Geneva and Lake Annecy with the Salève mountain in between. It is a mountainous region containing both very rural agricultural areas and densely populated towns and cities. The area is also a very popular tourism destination due to the presence of lakes and mountains and the host of activities on offer all year round. Besides CERN in Meyrin, other academic institutions are based in the region, including UNIGE¹¹ and HEPIA¹² in Geneva, EPFL¹³ and UNIL¹⁴ in Lausanne, ESI¹⁵ in Archamps, Les Houches School of Physics and the CNRS¹⁶, along with LAPP¹⁷ and LAPTh¹⁸ in Annecy on the USMB¹⁹ campus, which is also home to Polytech²⁰, an IAE²⁰ and an IUT²¹.

In view of the structure of the region and the siting of the FCC, we have identified six locations (see Illustration 10) as possible candidates for the location of the above-mentioned pole. These locations have been selected on the basis of several criteria: position on the southern side of the FCC, road access, points of interest (such as a nearby university campus) and proximity to the surface sites.

Our analysis therefore applies to the following locations (not presented in any order of preference):

- Scientific site PG, Charvonnex: Option 1 (O1)
- Groisy railway station: Option 2 (O2)
- LAPP/CNRS campus, Annecy: Option (O3)
- Scientific site PJ, Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens: Option 4 (O4)
- Commune of Éteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron: Option 5 (O5)
- Scientific site PD, Nangy/Contamine-sur-Arve/Fillinges: Option 6 (O6)

Other locations were considered but were deemed to be unsuitable:

- Villaz and Fillière (difficult to access, too rural, lack of appropriate facilities).

Annex 7.6 show the matrix of distances in kilometres and minutes with these options added. Annex 7.7 provides a SWOT analysis²² of each location.

¹¹ University of Geneva

¹² Geneva's school of landscaping, engineering and architecture, one of the Universities of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO)

¹³ Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne

¹⁴ University of Lausanne

¹⁵ European Scientific Institute

¹⁶ French National Centre for Scientific Research

¹⁷ Annecy particle physics laboratory

¹⁸ Annecy theoretical physics laboratory

¹⁹ University of Savoie Mont Blanc

²⁰ university school of management

²¹ university institute of technology

²² A SWOT analysis is a strategic analysis method used to assess the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of

Illustration 10: Potential options for the location of the pole.

If deemed appropriate, other locations may in future be envisaged together with stakeholders in the region.

Lastly, different scenarios will also be considered: a pole in a single location or a pole divided into several parts in different locations, depending on the nature of the activities.

The options presented are suggestions only and are not binding, either on CERN or on local stakeholders. These ideas will be open to discussion with local stakeholders.

an undertaking, organisation or project. It is used to identify the internal and external aspects that can influence the performance and strategy of an undertaking or project.

4.3 OPTION 1: SITE PG – CHARVONNEX/GROISY

4.3.1 Location profile

- Commune: Charvonnex
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 1428 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté d’agglomération du Grand Annecy
- Identity: rural

Site PG is located on a plateau that straddles the boundary between the communes of Charvonnex and Groisy some distance from residential areas and other facilities. The pole would be located on the same land as scientific site PG. If this option were chosen, sufficient space would need to be provided to construct the pole. This site, which will host an experiment, is likely to be one of the most important sites during the period that the FCC-ee is running.

Illustration 11 shows the location of the potential site and points of interest within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 11: Location of site option 1 at Charvonnex and facilities in the surrounding area.

4.3.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 7 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is assigned a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 7: Pole location criteria scores for option 1.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Reasonable (17.7 km, 22 min)	3
Proximity to scientific site PG	Satisfactory (on the same site)	5
Adequate proximity to the other sites	All sites except PF are distant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (40.6 km – 41 min) - PB (39.8 km – 38 min) - PD (28.2 km – 24 min) - PF (13.2 km – 12 min) - PJ (41.3 km – 39 min) - PL (43.9 km – 45 min) 	3
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D1203 – A410 (Cruseilles) Rail network: Groisy station (Léman Express) (4.7 km – 8 min) Bus network: “Le Clémone” stop (1 km – 1 min): route 80	3
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Few local services and shops: Small number of pizzeria-style restaurants (1.2 km–1.4 km) Bakery (1 km) No accommodation Grocery stores and similar selling local produce (1.6 km), Carrefour Market supermarket (2.4 km) Post office (4 km)	2
Proximity to conference centres	No conference centres in the immediate vicinity Conference centres in Annecy (12 km)	3
Proximity to universities	No universities in the immediate vicinity Annecy campus with USMB and research laboratories including LAPP (12 km)	3
Proximity to emergency services	Groisy-Thorens fire station (2 km) Annecy Genevois Hospital (9 km)	5
Proximity to contractors	Le Plot-Longchamp industrial estates: few contractors (2 km) Industrial estates in Argonay, Epagny Metz-Tessy and Annecy (7 km)	5

4.3.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Our analysis of the urban development documentation (including the ScoT and PLU strategic planning documents) has identified the following potential opportunities and synergies:

- Possibility of opening a rail halt on the site of the former railway station at Doucy, which would boost urban development centred on this area → the presence of a scientific facility would strengthen the case for this halt.
- Desire to promote sustainable transport, in particular cycle paths to the D1203 road (providing a cycle route to Annecy) and to Mercier Saint-Martin-de-Bellevue railway station → CERN could make sustainable modes of transport available to its personnel (such as e-bikes and e-scooters or a shuttle service).
- Desire to strengthen the link between producers and consumers and encourage short supply chains → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.
- Desire to develop the tourism economy → the presence of a scientific pole has the potential to encourage tourism (the visitor centre would be open to scientists and tourists).
- Desire to encourage local green tourism → science tourism can go hand in hand with green tourism by promoting local tourism (consumption of local produce, eco-friendly overnight accommodation, combining a visit of the scientific site with exploring the local countryside such as the banks of the River Fillière).
- Desire to develop small-scale tourism accommodation facilities (gîte holiday rentals, farm camp sites) → possible partnerships between these facilities and the pole/CERN.
- Presence of a secondary school and plans for a new secondary school in nearby Groisy → possibility of creating a science training and education link with the pole and these secondary schools.

Meetings with representatives of the commune:

Meetings between the representatives of the commune of Charvonnex and the FCC team working on opportunities resulted in discussions regarding the benefits of drawing on the synergy created by the presence of a scientific site (and possibly of a CERN pole) in developing the commune (food offer, tourism activities, cultural centre with swimming pool, agricultural activity, etc.). These services could also make use of the heat emitted by the FCC equipment. Groisy municipal council, which also has land available, is keen to use the opportunity of the scientific site for local development. Given that these two communes are next to each other, it will be helpful to develop this thinking jointly. For example, one commune could host the pole and the other could develop services serving the pole.

4.4 OPTION 2: GROISY

4.4.1 Location profile

- Commune: Groisy
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 3900 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté d’agglomération du Grand Annecy
- Identity: rural

This potential location is in the commune of Groisy on the site of the recycling company Excoffier next to Groisy railway station. This 2.5-hectare site is near site PG in Groisy/Charvonnex. A business located opposite this site is also likely to be moving, which will free up an additional hectare of land.

Illustration 12 shows the potential location of the pole and the facilities within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 12: Location of site option 2 at Groisy and facilities in the surrounding area.

4.4.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 8 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is given a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 8: Pole location criteria scores for option 2.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Satisfactory (15.2 km – 20 min)	4
Proximity to scientific site PG	Close (4.7 km – 8 min)	5
Adequate proximity to the other sites	All sites except PF are distant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (39.4 km – 41 min) - PB (40.9 km – 39 min) - PD (27 km – 27 min) - PF (12 km – 14 min) - PJ (29.6 km – 39 min) - PL (43 km – 43 min) 	3
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D1203 – D2 – A410 (Cruseilles) Rail network: Groisy Thorens station (Léman Express) Bus network: “Groisy Gare” stop (poor facilities)	4
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Few local services and shops: Small number of restaurants Bakery No accommodation Shops/grocery stores Post office	2
Proximity to conference centres	No conference centres in the immediate vicinity Conference centres in Annecy (17 km)	3
Proximity to universities	No universities in the immediate vicinity Annecy campus with USMB and research laboratories including LAPP (17 km)	3
Proximity to emergency services	Groisy-Thorens fire station (2.7 km) Annecy Genevois Hospital (14 km)	5
Proximity to contractors	Le Plot-Longchamp industrial estates: few contractors (2 km) Industrial estates in Argonay, Epagny Metz-Tessy and Annecy (10.8 km)	4

4.4.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Our analysis of the urban development documentation (including the ScoT and PLU strategic planning documents) has identified the following potential opportunities and synergies:

- Development of sustainable transport (pedestrians, cycles) with the emphasis on provision of cycle paths → CERN could make sustainable modes of transport available to its personnel (such as e-bikes and e-scooters or a shuttle service).
- Support for the establishment of businesses and services in the centres of urban development (particularly above the Longchamp industrial estate → partnerships with the pole and existing and/or developing services would provide them with a boost and/or contribute to their development.
- Stepping up the role of Le Plot-Longchamp industrial estate as a centre for retail and small businesses. Expansion of the small-business zone and limited expansion of the ZACom retail park → partnerships with the pole and existing and/or developing services would provide them with a boost/contribute to their development due to the proximity of site PG and this commercial development zone.
- Permitting farm shops on local farms → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.
- Encouraging the development of small-scale accommodation facilities, including on farms (gîte holiday rentals) → it would also be desirable for the scientific pole to have tourism accommodation facilities; possible partnerships between the two.
- Presence of a secondary school and plans for a new secondary school in nearby Groisy → possibility of creating a science training and education link with the pole and these secondary schools.

Meetings with representatives of the commune:

Meetings between the representatives of the commune of Groisy and the FCC team working on synergies resulted in discussions regarding the opportunity to use such a pole as the basis for a collaboration. The site currently occupied by Excoffier, along with another site located opposite, are likely to be vacated, providing a surface area of 3.5 hectares. Furthermore, the area around the railway station has development potential for the municipal council. The objective is to develop the station into a multimodal interchange hub, which would include the construction of an additional railway track. This could lead to development opportunities in the area around the railway station and interchange hub. The FCC could strengthen the case for building the additional railway track at the station. The municipal council already has Groisy campus²³, which is set to expand, and therefore already has experience of accommodating such a site. It also has a secondary school, with a second school due to open nearby in the very near future, which is of interest from the point of view of establishing educational links. Accommodating a pole of this kind would go hand in hand with the desire to develop the local area. This would involve providing services such as offices for the pole, accommodation facilities, restaurants and other services. These amenities could be developed in collaboration with Charvonnex municipal council. The facilities and services could be shared between the two communes but developed strategically and jointly. These services could also make use of the heat generated by the FCC.

²³ A centre for work placement training in the food trades, catering, pharmacy and floristry.

4.5 OPTION 3: CNRS/LAPP ANNECY

4.5.1 Location profile

- Commune: Annecy
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 130 721 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté d'agglomération du Grand Annecy
- Identity: urban

This location analysis concerns the Annecy university campus and more specifically the site of the CNRS/IN2P3 laboratory: Annecy particle physics laboratory (LAPP). LAPP/CNRS occupies a site of 20 000 m² (on a long-term lease from the department), parts of which, totalling 12 000 m², are long-term unused (see Illustration 14).

Illustration 13 shows the potential location of the pole and the facilities within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 13: Location of site option 3 at Annecy and facilities in the surrounding area.

Box 2: More about the Annecy university campus and LAPP.

The university campus is located in the commune of Annecy-le-Vieux. In 2020 this campus of approximately 14 hectares accommodated some 5000 students and more than 800 people working at the universities and research centres. There are plans to increase this to up to 8000 students by 2025. The following facilities are present on the site:

Education:

- USMB (University of Savoie Mont Blanc, based in Chambéry, with three campuses: Le Bourget-du-Lac, Jacob-Bellecombette and Annecy)
- IUT
- IAE
- Polytech'
- TETRAS (work placement training)

Research:

- Maison de la Mécatronique/SYMME
- LAPP
- LAPTh
- LISTIC (computer science)
- IREGE (management and economics)

Planned:

- MAPI (Maison de l'Action Publique et Internationale), to offer courses in economics, law and modern languages, plus research laboratories. To be built in 2024.

CNRS/LAPP was established in 1976 on the initiative of Paris-based CNRS physicists with a view to working more closely with CERN. LAPP now collaborates on various CERN projects (currently ATLAS, LHCb and the FCC). Some 150 people work there (29% research scientists and lecturers conducting research), 55% in administrative and technical support, 10% postgraduate students and 6% post-doctoral researchers), 50 of whom work directly with CERN (see Annex 7.8).

LAPP is an important regional laboratory conducting, for example, the IDEFICS project²⁴ in partnership with Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region, which helps businesses in the region achieve digital transition through its digital platform MUST²⁵. It is also worth mentioning the EUTOPIA²⁶ project and its Discovery Space, designed to educate and inform the general public about advances in physics and technology (in partnership with Grand Annecy, the Haute-Savoie department and Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region).

²⁴ <https://idefics.fr/en/>

²⁵ <https://www.lapp.in2p3.fr/centre-de-calcul-must>

²⁶ <https://eutopia-annecy.in2p3.fr/>

Illustration 14: Aerial view of the LAPP/CNRS site.

Legend:

- 1. Currently: car park – Potentially: science and research campus? – 5500 m²
- 2. Currently: Green spaces – Potentially: keep the green spaces but make better use of them? – 6000 m²
- 3. Currently: Car park – Potentially: restaurant? Other? – 900 m²
- 4. Currently: Green spaces – Potentially: extension of auditorium? – 300 m²

Area 1, outlined in orange, currently contains a car park which is likely to be removed in the future. It covers approximately 5500 m² and could potentially accommodate the FCC pole.

For information, this campus is near the Parc des Glaisins industrial estate. The Annecy strategic development plan is looking at ways of strengthening the links between the Parc des Glaisins and the university campus.

4.5.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 9 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is given a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 9: Pole location criteria scores for option 3.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Reasonable (26.8 km – 31 min)	2
Proximity to scientific site PG	Close (12.3 km – 15 min)	4
Adequate proximity to the other sites	Sites are distant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (48.8 km – 44 min) - PB (51.3 km – 45 min) - PD (43.2 km – 32 min) - PF (25.2 km – 26 min) - PJ (37.5 km – 42 min) - PL (52.1 km – 50 min) 	2
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D2201 – D916 – A41 Rail network: Annecy station (Léman Express) (5 km) Bus network: “Campus” stop (routes 1 and 4) serving the railway station	5
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Currently few services on the campus itself Many services, shops and restaurants and multiple accommodation options (hotels, gîte holiday rentals, furnished holiday apartments, chambres d’hôtes B&B) in Annecy Post office	5
Proximity to conference centres	Conference centres in Annecy: Imperial Congress Centre, capacity 600 (3.4 km) Meeting centre, capacity 650 (1.8 km) (Parc des Glaisins) Centre Bonlieu, capacity 900 (3.9 km) LAPP auditorium, capacity 250	5
Proximity to universities	Annecy campus with USMB and research laboratories, including LAPP (which collaborates in CERN experiments)	5
Proximity to emergency services	Fire and rescue centre (4.4 km) Annecy Genevois Hospital (7 km)	5
Proximity to contractors	Many industrial estates in Annecy Very close to the Parc des Glaisins Near the Argonay and Epagny Metz-Tessy industrial estates	5

4.5.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Our analysis of the urban development documentation (including the ScoT and PLU strategic planning documents) has identified the following potential opportunities and synergies:

- Encouraging the development of and continuing to improve the facilities at the university/research pole. Plans to expand the university pole and add to the university sporting facilities → hosting this research pole is compatible. In addition, the pole would work in collaboration with LAPP, which is already on site. Possibility of educational partnerships between CERN and the educational establishments on the site.
- Retaining the space required to expand the university/research pole, adding teaching and research buildings and facilities → hosting the pole is compatible.
- Improving public transport provision for the university/research pole along with connections between the pole and the centre of Annecy and the town of Annecy in general → ensuring that the campus is connected to different centres enhances its legitimacy.
- Developing synergies between the university/research pole and Les Glaisins industrial estate → depending on the location of the pole, these synergies can help strengthen links between these two entities.
- Desire to improve rail connections with Chambéry/Grenoble and Geneva → Annecy university campus already has links with Chambéry and Grenoble through the relationships that USMB and LAPP maintain with the universities there.
- Developing cycle paths or greenways that interconnect with neighbouring areas.
- Desire to encourage the expansion of the industrial estates, particularly the one at Les Glaisins (an “emblematic regional zone”) by developing services of all kinds. Improving local services on the Les Glaisins site → a pole of this kind requires local services that can be developed jointly through partnerships.
- Desire to develop the industry niches for which the Annecy urban area has a regional and national reputation (particularly engineering, mechatronics, and image and multimedia technology) → an infrastructure like the FCC requires advanced engineering, mechatronics and computer science skills.
- Encouraging the implementation of a strategy designed to boost the area through innovation and by supporting creativity and the quest for excellence in technology and corporate management through training and the promotion of centres of excellence → the FCC pole supports the quest for excellence, particularly in technology, through innovation and the creation of education and training relevant to both CERN and the higher education establishments.
- Developing short distribution chains (producer-to-consumer chains) → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.
- Desire to promote and develop Annecy’s tourism appeal: encouraging and supporting year-round tourism by further developing business tourism, particularly through the exhibition, seminar and congress centre at Albigny → a research infrastructure of this kind is a vector of business tourism demand, particularly where many workshops involving scientists engaged in the collaborations are organised.
- Desire to develop USMB in the Annecy basin through links with the other universities in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes and the Geneva area → the pole would create an opportunity to reinforce links between USMB and the Geneva universities given that CERN already works together with the Geneva universities.

- Developing the innovative industry sectors in which the Annecy area would be able to develop specialities and create jobs for graduates. Desire to boost the area's ability to attract leading businesses by providing a higher education offer relevant to the area's specialised economic profile . Premium services and higher education will help boost the knowledge economy, a component of the economy essential to ensuring competitiveness and to maintaining a broad share of the productive economy → CERN is already active in knowledge sharing, working with leading businesses and in partnership with higher education institutions. The presence of a pole in this area would further develop this knowledge locally. CERN recruits a large number of recent graduates in a wide variety of fields.

Hosting this pole is consistent with the vision of the Grand Annecy intercommunal structure. Ideally, the pole would be on the university campus, where it would create synergies with Greater Annecy's long-term vision (providing a home for a research centre of excellence and boosting the development of the campus, among other things). All of the above-mentioned reasons are compatible with locating a pole here. This positioning is challenged by, among other things, the high demand for real-estate.

4.6 OPTION 4: SITE PJ – DINGY-EN-VUACHE/VULBENS

4.6.1 Location profile

- Commune: Dingy-en-Vuache
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 700 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes du Genevois
- Identity: rural

- Commune: Vulbens
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 1600 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes du Genevois
- Identity: rural

- Commune: Valleiry
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 4866 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes du Genevois
- Identity: rural

The potential location of this option for the pole has not been decided. It could be on or near the site under consideration for site PJ.

Illustration 15 shows the potential location of the pole and the facilities within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 15: Location of site option 4 at Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens and facilities in the surrounding area.

4.6.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 10 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is given a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 10: Pole location criteria scores for option 4.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Satisfactory (15.2 km – 21 min)	4
Proximity to scientific site PG	Distant (41.3 km – 39 min)	2
Adequate proximity to the other sites	All sites except PL are distant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (34.2 km – 35 min) - PB (34.4 km – 36 min) - PD (38.4 km – 34 min) - PF (50.1 km – 41 min) - PL (20.1 km – 20 min) 	2
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D1206 – D7 – A40 Rail network: Valleiry station (2.7 km)	3
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Local services and shops: Small number of restaurants Bakery No accommodation Shops/grocery stores Post office Valleiry retail park	2
Proximity to conference centres	No conference centres in the immediate vicinity	1
Proximity to universities	No universities in the immediate vicinity	1
Proximity to emergency services	Vuache fire and rescue centre (1.7 km) Annecy Genevois Hospital in Saint-Julien-en-Genevois (15.3 km)	5
Proximity to contractors	Grands Chavannoux industrial estates Vulbens/Valleiry: few contractors Archamps Technopole (17.7 km)	3

4.6.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Meetings with representatives of the communes:

A new secondary school (collège) for 700 students has recently been opened in the commune of Vulbens. It would be desirable to create science education links with scientific site PJ. In addition, having a scientific research site with a collège nearby could prompt proposals to also build a new high school (lycée). Furthermore, there is considerable enthusiasm for the idea of having a visitor centre for site PJ given that there is currently no tourism activity locally. Since the Grands Chavannoux industrial estate is flourishing, building a scientific pole nearby could boost its development, with additional services becoming available. This industrial estate could expand onto land opposite the collège (more than nine hectares available). These services could make use of the heat emitted by the FCC equipment. The pole could therefore strengthen the development of these communes and encourage the link between the current stakeholders and scientific research.

4.7 OPTION 5: LA ROCHE-SUR-FORON

4.7.1 Location profile

- Commune: La Roche-sur-Foron
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 11 149 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes du Pays Rochois
- Identity: urban

- Commune: Éteaux
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 2021 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes du Pays Rochois
- Identity: rural

The following analysis is not based on a particular location. Since surface site PF is fairly remote, it is not being considered as a location for the pole. On the other hand, the commune of La Roche-sur-Foron appears to be a more suitable location to develop the pole. That said, site PF is a technical site of lesser importance and not suitable for development as a scientific site.

Illustration 16 shows the potential location of the pole and the facilities within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 16: Location of site option 6 at La Roche-sur-Foron and facilities in the surrounding area.

4.7.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 11 Table 12 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is given a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 11: Pole location criteria scores for option 5.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Reasonable (35.6 km – 30 min)	2
Proximity to scientific site PG	Close (13.2 km – 12 min)	4
Adequate proximity to the other sites	All sites except PD and PF are distant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (49.3 km – 40 min) - PB (26.2 km – 27 min) - PD (14.5 km – 12 min) - PF (immediate vicinity) - PJ (50.1 km – 41 min) - PL (52.7 km – 47 min) 	3
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D1203 – D2 – A410 Rail network: La Roche-sur-Foron station (Léman Express) Bus network: Proxim'iTi network	4
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Large number of shops Large number of restaurants Many accommodation options (hotels, gîte holiday rentals, furnished holiday apartments, chambres d'hôtes B&B, etc.) Post office	5
Proximity to conference centres	Roch'Expo in the immediate vicinity (conference capacity of up to 1000 seats)	5
Proximity to universities	No universities in the immediate vicinity	1
Proximity to emergency services	Pays Rochois fire and rescue centre in Éteaux (3.2 km)	5
Proximity to contractors	Near the Arve Valley A large number of industrial estates in the north of the commune	5

4.7.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Our analysis of the urban development documentation (including the ScoT and PLU strategic planning documents) has identified the following potential opportunities and synergies:

- Enhancing the area's business environment through the activity of Roch'Expo conference centre → the presence of the pole could boost activity at the conference centre by adding a scientific component.
- Desire to benefit from a clear economic position to maintain an identity separate from the Geneva metropolis by reaffirming the Pays Rochois' role, hosting international events and strengthening its partnership with Roch'Expo with the ambition of being on a par with Palexpo in Geneva → CERN's science for all policy is implemented mainly through organising international conferences and events.
- Desire to encourage farmers to become involved in initiatives encouraging short supply chains → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.
- Desire to improve how the business park functions and to encourage significant change and efforts to optimise them (industry and retail particularly) → in addition to its scientific side, CERN and its infrastructures have a significant industrial component.
- Supporting and attracting economic stakeholders and improving links between the different centres of industry and business and the town as a whole, plus the desire of elected representatives to boost the economic activity of their local area → CERN's presence in the Pays de Gex has attracted economic players and encouraged the establishment of new innovative businesses in connection with the technologies used at CERN.
- Desire to develop a single tourism strategy promoting the Pays Rochois area as a thriving area (particularly through exhibitions) → CERN organises many exhibitions about the scientific research it carries out.
- Desire to develop leisure tourism with a varied accommodation offer → possibility of partnerships with the pole to help to develop this offer.
- Desire to create a more coherent relationship between business tourism and local economic development → developing business tourism associated with the international collaboration on the scientific sites.
- Desire to promote and boost the tourism sector, particularly "nature tourism" (possible additional income source for farmers) → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.

4.8 OPTION 6: SITE PD – NANGY

4.8.1 Location profile

- Commune: Nangy
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 1604 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes Arve et Salève
- Identity: rural

- Commune: Contamine-sur-Arve
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 2090 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes Faucigny-Glières
- Identity: rural

- Commune: Fillinges
- Department: Haute-Savoie
- Population: 3516 inhabitants (2019)
- Intercommunal structure: Communauté de communes des Quatre Rivières
- Identity: rural

Ideally, the pole would be located close to scientific site PD. If this location is chosen for the pole, the site will need to be big enough to accommodate it. The initial idea was to locate the pole on site PD but if desired it could be located in the neighbouring communes depending on the options available.

Illustration 17 shows the potential location of the pole and the facilities within a radius of approximately 30 minutes.

Illustration 17: Location of site option 5 at Nangy and facilities in the surrounding area.

4.8.2 Pole location criteria scores

Table 12 summarises the criteria required for the smooth operation of the pole. Each criterion is given a score, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

Table 12: Pole location criteria scores for option 6.

Criterion	Comments	Score
Proximity to technical site PH	Reasonable (40.3 km – 31 min)	2
Proximity to scientific site PG	Borderline acceptable (28.2 km – 24 min)	3
Adequate proximity to the other sites	Adequate distance from all sites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PA (38 km – 34 min) - PB (14.6 km – 18 min) - PD (same location) - PF (14.5 km – 12 min) - PJ (38.4 km – 34 min) - PL (41.2 km – 42 min) 	4
Proximity to public transport and accessibility	Road network: D903 – D1205 – A40 Rail network: Reignier station (Léman Express) (5.6 km) – Annemasse station (Léman Express) (11 km) – La Roche-sur-Foron station (Léman Express) (10 km) Bus network: stop in Contamine-sur-Arve: Hôpital Findrol (400 m); TAC route 5, TAD, Proxim'iti route 274	4
Proximity to services, amenities and shops	Near the industrial estates in Findrol, small number of businesses: restaurants and a bakery “Entre Parenthèse” restaurant at the hospital (CHAL) Ibis Budget Nangy (2 stars), Campanile Findrol Savoie Léman (3 stars) Post office	5
Proximity to conference centres	No conference centres in the immediate vicinity Roch'Expo (12.3 km)	3
Proximity to universities	No universities in the immediate vicinity UNIGE, HEPIA (17 km)	3
Proximity to emergency services	Pays Rochois fire and rescue centre in Éteaux (12.9 km) Alpes-Léman Hospital (CHAL) (400 m)	4
Proximity to contractors	Near the Arve Valley Near the industrial estates in Annemasse and Ville-la-Grand	5

4.8.3 Opportunities and synergies with the local area

Our analysis of the urban development documentation (including the ScoT and PLU strategic planning documents) has identified the following potential opportunities and synergies:

- The science and research pole requires local services (particularly restaurants and accommodation → partnerships with the pole and existing services and/or services currently being developed would provide them with a boost/help them to develop.
- Desire to pursue a project to develop an industrial estate into one emblematic for the Cœur du Faucigny area → since the site location is already close to an industrial estate, a scientific research pole would support this endeavour.
- Desire to encourage the purchase of local produce → the pole requires a food offer (grocery stores/restaurants). CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area.
- Desire to benefit from a resident economy → the presence of a scientific pole with ties to the local area would boost resident employment.
- Desire to develop centres of interest to attract tourists and pursue the tourism policies already being implemented (industrial tourism for example) → possibility of developing scientific and industrial tourism in connection with the pole.
- Encouraging tourism activities such as farm holiday accommodation and educational farms → the scientific pole would also wish to develop tourism accommodation facilities: possible partnerships between the pole and these accommodation providers.

Meetings with Haute-Savoie Departmental Council

Haute-Savoie Departmental Council has expressed interest in a pole of this kind being located close to scientific site PD.

4.9 SUMMARY

4.9.1 Recap of the advantages and disadvantages of each option

Table 13 sums up the main advantages and disadvantages of each option.

Table 13: Advantages and disadvantages of each option.

Option	Advantages	Disadvantages
Option 1 Site PG – Charvonnex / Groisy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for the opportunity to accommodate a pole and develop the local area in synergy Proximity of LAPP / CNRS and the university campus Scientific site PG will host a large experiment Good location with respect to the different FCC sites Groisy railway station 	Few services in the immediate vicinity
Option 2 Groisy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for the opportunity to accommodate a pole and develop the local area in synergy Land available Proximity of LAPP / CNRS and the university campus Proximity of scientific site PG hosting a large experiment Good location with respect to the different FCC sites Very close to Groisy railway station 	Few services in the immediate vicinity
Option 3 LAPP Annecy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support from Grand Annecy for the opportunity to accommodate a pole and develop the local area in synergy Presence of LAPP/CNRS and the university campus, plus USMB and other universities Land already available Proximity of scientific site PG Urban commune Railway station Local services in Annecy Good public transport offer Conference centres 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Few services on the campus but these are being developed, particularly in relation to the Parc des Glaisins industrial estate Distant from the other sites

<p>Option 4 Site PJ – Dingy-en-Vuache / Vulbens</p>	<p>Support for the opportunity to accommodate a pole and develop the local area in synergy</p> <p>Development under way in the local area: a new secondary school was recently opened and the industrial estate is being developed</p> <p>Land available on site PJ</p> <p>Scientific site hosting an experiment</p>	<p>Distant from sites PB, PD and PF</p> <p>Rural commune</p> <p>Few services in the immediate vicinity</p>
<p>Option 5 La Roche-sur-Foron</p>	<p>Urban area</p> <p>Conference centre</p> <p>Local services</p> <p>Near the Arve Valley</p>	<p>Technical site not suitable for development</p> <p>Site PF is a long way from the commune of La Roche-sur-Foron</p> <p>The municipal council has no known ambitions to develop the site</p> <p>No land available as far as we know</p>
<p>Option 6 Site PD – Nangy</p>	<p>Support from the Departmental Council for the opportunity to accommodate a pole and develop the local area in synergy</p> <p>Near the Arve Valley</p> <p>Proximity of the hospital</p>	<p>Distant from site PH</p> <p>Rural commune</p> <p>No land available as far as we know</p> <p>The municipal council has no known ambitions to develop the site</p>

4.9.2 Multicriteria analysis to determine the best location option

To carry out this multicriteria analysis we followed the following methodology:

- The 13 criteria set out above (i) were given a weighting (W) to take into account their importance relative to the other criteria (see Table 14).
- A score value from 1 to 5 (V) was given to each criterion, with 1 being the least satisfactory and 5 being the most satisfactory score with respect to each criterion. To give a value to the distance, a distance score was determined (see Table 15).
- The score for each option (S) was calculated by multiplying the weighting of each criterion (Wi) by its respective score value (Vi).

This resulted in the following formula being applied to each option:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{13} W_i \times V_i$$

Table 14: The criteria and their importance weightings.

Number	Criterion	Weighting
1	Proximity to site PH	0.18
2	Proximity to site PJ	0.08
3	Proximity to site PG	0.1
4	Proximity to site PF	0.03
5	Proximity to site PD	0.08
6	Proximity to site PB	0.15
7	Road access	0.1
8	Public transport	0.1
9	Services	0.05
10	Conference facilities	0.01
11	Universities	0.01
12	Emergency services	0.1
13	Contractors	0.01
Total		1

Table 15: Multicriteria analysis and distance scoring.

Distance in minutes	Value
< 10	5
10 to 18	4
19 to 27	3
28 to 35	2
> 35	1

This methodology enabled us to calculate a score for each option and from that an option ranking, as shown in Table 16. The Excel document “FCC-2311211100-JGU_MCA_Pole-Scenarios_V3-en” and Annex 7.9 explain in more detail the criteria applied, the coefficient used and the resulting score for each option.

Table 16: The score calculated for each pole location option.

Option	Location	Ranking	Score
Option 6	Site PD – Nangy	1	3.49
Option 5	La Roche-sur-Foron	2	3.42
Option 3	LAPP Annecy	3	3.04
Option 1	Site PG – Charvonnex	4	3.03
Option 2	Groisy	5	3.01
Option 4	Site PJ – Vulbens	6	2.63

Option 6, on site PD at Nangy, appears to be the best location option for an FCC pole. Option 5, at La Roche-sur-Foron, is in second place.

Please note that this ranking is based on the criteria established by CERN which are tailored to its project. From the point of view of each local area, the criteria and weightings applied may be different.

Section 5 deals with our assumptions regarding the number of people present on each site to calculate the requirements in terms of the surface area and the potential construction cost of the pole.

5. SURFACE AREA AND COST

5.1 ASSUMPTIONS REGARDING THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE POTENTIALLY ASSOCIATED WITH THE POLE

Regarding our assumptions about the number of people associated with the pole, it is helpful to define the requirements during each phase along with the number of people associated with each phase and to state whether these people are required to be on site (see Table 17).

Table 17: Numbers of people present on each site for each phase.

	Construction	Installation	Operation	Annual maintenance	Long shutdown for upgrade
Period	10 years	5 years (overlaps with the construction phase)	8 months of each year	4 months of each year	1 year, once during the entire programme duration
Scientific site	40 to 300 workers	200 to 300 technicians	4 to 8 team members 12 to 16 technicians	100 technicians	200 to 300 technicians
Technical site	20 to 130 workers	100 technicians	0 to 9 technicians	15 to 30 technicians	100 technicians

During the construction period the workers will stay on each site because they will be building the infrastructure. This is not especially relevant to the pole.

The same applies to the installation period.

During the operational period (operation, annual maintenance and long shutdown for upgrade), personnel will travel to and from the sites frequently.

Illustration 18, previously shown in section 0 of this document (Objective), presents several possibilities regarding the different categories of personnel associated with the pole. These possibilities are based on the assumption that the pole will serve sites PB, PF, PG, PH and PD. Since the best options are in the vicinity of site PD, it is logical that the pole should also accommodate the people whose work is connected with this site.

Illustration 18: Different possibilities for accommodating FCC personnel on the pole.

Possibility A: In the case of the team involved in the scientific collaboration on site (the people permanently present in the area), we can assume approximately 2000 people for one experiment and 2400 people for two experiments (one small and one large experiment). That said, a scientific collaboration can only function if physicists and engineers are also involved. Most of the time, these people prefer to be present on a CERN campus. If the new pole does not have the feel of a proper campus, with services and modern buildings providing team workspaces and facilities for meetings and even conferences, there is little chance that these physicists and engineers will come and work permanently on this pole. It is unlikely that the entire collaboration will be permanently present on this pole, but the people required to travel regularly to the infrastructure might prefer to be permanently present there. Be that as it may, the members of the team running the experiment during the operational phase have to be present on the site where the experiment is based. If the pole is located on the same site as an experiment, there will be a minimum of four to eight people working in the control room on this pole. On the other hand, if the pole is located elsewhere, it is likely that these team members will remain where the experiment is based, in the control rooms built on the surface site itself. That said, advances in automation raise the prospect of an experiment being run entirely remotely in a few years' time.

Possibility B: In the case of the team specialising in one technology for the whole of the FCC, the fact that there are several such technologies means that there are several possibilities. This will depend chiefly on the location of these technologies. Some will be present around the whole of the accelerator or on all sites but others will be present on certain sites only. For example, the superconducting radiofrequency system will be present mainly on site PH and to a lesser extent on site PL. These two sites will also accommodate the cryogenics system, with most of this being on site PH. In general, one technology requires approximately 100 to 150 personnel. This means that if a team responsible for a technology for the whole of the FCC is to be accommodated on the pole, this could amount to around a hundred people.

Possibility C: In the case of the team specialising in one technology for one or more sectors of the FCC, the number of people involved is lower. The FCC will comprise a total of eight sectors. If 100 to 150 personnel look after one technology for the whole accelerator, it can be calculated that there will be approximately 15 personnel per sector. As stated above, the pole could serve sites PB, PF, PG and PH, and potentially also site PD. This would total approximately 70 people looking after the technology for the half of the FCC served by the pole even though, as stated above, some technologies are present on only one or two sites.

Possibility D: The last possibility considered here is a multidisciplinary team looking after part of the FCC. This is the case currently during the accelerator maintenance or upgrade work, which involves technicians with different specialisms coming in to inspect, repair, install or upgrade the infrastructure and associated systems. During operation, we can assume approximately 5 technicians per technical site and 15 per scientific site. During annual maintenance, we can assume 100 technicians per scientific site and 20 technicians per technical site. During the shutdown for the upgrade, we can assume 250 technicians per scientific site and 100 per technical site. These technicians will often have to travel to the sites from their workplace or home. A pole could therefore accommodate these people who travel regularly to inspect the accelerator and its systems. Given that the upgrade work will take place only once during the entire FCC-ee programme, this estimate is based mainly on the annual maintenance personnel figures. Based on a geographical division of half of the infrastructure being served by the existing CERN campus and half by an additional pole, it is likely that the new pole will have to accommodate approximately 250 people.

Illustration 19: Possibilities for accommodating FCC personnel on the pole (approximate figures). summarises the different possibilities adding the approximate numbers of personnel present.

Illustration 19: Possibilities for accommodating FCC personnel on the pole (approximate figures).

These possibilities may also be cumulative. It is not yet possible to say with any certainty whether any given possibility will arise or which possibility will arise since this will depend on a number of factors.

5.2 SURFACE AREA AND COST ESTIMATES

5.2.1 Surface area estimate

AFNOR standard NF X 35-102²⁷ recommends a minimum surface area of 10 m² per person in neutral working environments and up to 15 m² in noisy areas. Given that it is too early to determine the type of offices required, we propose to use an average figure of 12 m² per person²⁸. In general, 20% is added to the figure for office space to allow for circulation spaces, sanitary facilities, communal areas, service rooms and the like. Provision is made for a margin of error by adding 10% to the total surface area calculated. Based on the different construction projects for office buildings at CERN, the number of square metres calculated per person is generally 15 (including sanitary facilities, meeting rooms and corridors). Table 18 summarises the potential surface area of the pole for each possibility outlined above.

Table 18: Surface area estimates for the pole based on the different personnel possibilities.

Possibility A	Possibility B	Possibility C	Possibility D
Team involved in the scientific collaboration on site	Team specialising in one technology for the whole of the FCC	Team specialising in one technology for one or more sectors of the FCC	Multidisciplinary team looking after part of the FCC
2400 people	120 people	70 people	250 people
36 000 m ²	1800 m ²	1100 m ²	3800 m ²

These figures assume a building for office use only. If we include communal areas, cafeterias, an auditorium, reception and educational areas, and laboratories, these surface areas will differ considerably.

5.2.2 Cost estimate

The construction cost will also vary considerably depending on the materials used, the geographical location, the complexity of the design and local construction standards. According to CERN’s Site and Civil Engineering Department, costs vary from 2000 to 2500 EUR, and up to 3000 EUR per m² in Haute-Savoie. For example, an office building using timber materials currently being constructed at CERN in Switzerland costs approximately 3000 EUR + VAT per m². This figure is generally increased by 15 to 20% to cover design and construction supervision fees and for land surveys, legal costs and other surveys²⁹.

Table 19 shows an approximation of the total construction cost of the pole as an office building for each of the possibilities considered, assuming a cost of 2500 EUR per m².

²⁷ French ergonomics standard – Ergonomic design of work spaces in offices

²⁸ Average calculated for a single employee as used by commercial real estate organisations such as the firm Cushman & Wakefield (<https://immobilier.cushmanwakefield.fr/nos-conseils/conseil/mesurer-surface-bureaux>) and BNP Paribas Real Estate (<https://www.bnppre.fr/guides/guides-conseils/immobilier-tertiaire-comment-calculer-sa-surface-de-bureau.html>).

²⁹ Based on conversations with CERN’s Site and Civil Engineering Department

Table 19: Estimate of the total construction cost of a pole for each personnel possibility considered.

Possibility A	Possibility B	Possibility C	Possibility D
2400 people	120 people	70 people	250 people
36 000 m ²	1800 m ²	1100 m ²	3800 m ²
90 MEUR	4.5 MEUR	2.8 MEUR	9.5 MEUR

These estimates are for a building exclusively for office use and make no allowance for the development of a pole with different services. For a pole with more extensive facilities, we can take as a reference point Building B777 currently being constructed at CERN, which will comprise offices, meeting rooms, laboratories, team workspaces and a restaurant. It will be 13 000 m² in size, accommodate 475 people and has cost approximately 48.3 MEUR.

These initial figures are rough preliminary estimates only, based on the information available to date. The surface area required and costs may vary considerably depending on the technologies used, the working methods and also taking into account the long time horizon.

6. CONCLUSION

With reference to four possibilities regarding the number of personnel to be accommodated on the pole built to serve sites PB, PD, PF, PG and PH, we can assume personnel numbers ranging from 70 to 2400, a surface area of 1100 to 36 000 m² and a cost of 2.8 MEUR to 90 MEUR. These figures could be cumulative given that the pole could accommodate both a collaboration and the personnel required to run the accelerator. Table 20 summarises the estimated numbers of personnel, surface areas and costs of the potential pole for each possibility.

Table 20: Summary of personnel numbers, surface areas and costs of the pole for each possibility.

Possibility A	Possibility B	Possibility C	Possibility D
1 team (scientific collaboration)	1 specialised team	1 specialised team	1 multidisciplinary team
1 or 2 experiments	1 technology for the whole of the FCC	1 technology for one or more sectors of the FCC	Several technologies for one or more sectors of the FCC
2400 people	120 people	70 people	250 people
36 000 m ²	1800 m ²	1100 m ²	3800 m ²
90 MEUR	4.5 MEUR	2.8 MEUR	9.5 MEUR

Regarding the location of the pole, option 6 (on site PD at Nangy) and option 5 (La Roche-sur-Foron) are the two options that best meet the different criteria established for the smooth running of the FCC. This ranking does not discount the other proposed locations. It is also possible to conceive of a pole divided up over several locations should this be deemed appropriate. The map in Illustration 20: Locations and ranking of the options. shows the locations of the options with the best options shown in green, the ones in the middle of the ranking in orange and the location at the bottom of the ranking in red.

Illustration 20: Locations and ranking of the options.

However, the number of people present on the pole and its location depend on different factors. For the moment it is difficult to say how the infrastructure’s technical systems will be organised, how they will function and how they will be operated. This will have an impact on the number of people required on site to run the infrastructure. In addition, depending on the attitudes to work, home life and commuting of the people involved in the programme, their willingness to be located on a new pole is highly variable and subjective. The level of services on offer, the modernity of the building and the scientific environment there are factors that will influence the presence of people on this pole. As for its location, this will also depend on the willingness of local stakeholders to accommodate and/or develop it. To ensure better integration of the pole into the local area, it is essential to limit its environmental impact with respect to the landscape, the waste it generates and its energy use. With sustainable regional development in mind, increasing numbers of municipal councils are keen to develop a local area where everything is accessible within a 15-minute radius. Taking this dimension into account would help ensure that the pole is better integrated into the local area. Depending on the location of the pole and the receptiveness of the local stakeholders, it would also be preferable for the pole to be not simply an office building but also a community space where scientists work together and a cultural space able to accommodate visitors, collaborations with businesses, and educational and training facilities. This will only be possible through cooperation with the local stakeholders.

7. ANNEXES

7.1 LIST OF INSTALLATIONS ON THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL SITES

Table 21: List of infrastructures and installations on the surface sites during the operational phase of the FCC-ee.

Category	Infrastructure and installation	Scientific site	Technical site
Site and logistics	Facilities specific to the site such as car parks, roads and fencing.	X	X
	Space to unload materials and equipment and for trucks to manoeuvre and turn.	X	X
Access to underground area	A lift in the primary shaft providing access to the service cavern and technical systems.	X	X
	Another lift in the secondary shaft providing access to the experiment cavern.	X	
	A building for the transfer of equipment between the surface and underground (including a radiological analysis station).	X	X
Technical installations	A station to produce and supply compressed air.	X	X
	A station for storing and supplying the experiment with working gas.	X	X
	Power converters and other electrical equipment, plus an electrical substation.	X	X
	A tunnel ventilation station near the secondary shaft.	X	X
	An experiment ventilation station.	X	
	A water pumping station with cooling towers.	X	X
	A water cooling station with heat exchangers.	X	X
	A discharge water treatment station.	X	X
	A station to convert electrical energy to radiofrequency energy for particle acceleration (sites PH and PL).		X
	A cryogenic cooling system (sites PH and PL).		X
	Liquid helium reservoirs (sites PH and PL).		X

Experiment	A building next to the main shaft for installation of the experiment (assembly, testing and installation hall) and providing access to the main cavern. Storage buildings.	X	
	Workshops (can be incorporated in the experiment assembly hall).	X	
	A building containing offices and meeting rooms, plus a control room.	X	
	A computing centre (can be incorporated into the building containing offices and meeting rooms).	X	
Storage	An area for temporary unloading and storage.	X	X
Safety	Installations for the protection of persons such as first-aid equipment and equipment for use by the emergency services.	X	X
Vegetation	Places designed to renature the site (will vary from site to site).	X	X
Water retention basin	A basin for storing discharged cooling water.	X	X

7.2 EXPERIMENTS AND TECHNICAL SYSTEMS OF AN ACCELERATOR

The list of technical systems presented below is not exhaustive.

7.2.1 Scientific site with a detector for an experiment

What is an experiment located on a scientific site?

The experiments use detectors to analyse the myriad particles produced by collisions in the accelerator. These experiments are run by collaborations of scientists from research institutes all over the world. Each experiment is distinct and characterised by its detectors.

The two largest experiments use general-purpose detectors to investigate the broadest range of physics possible. Having two independently designed detectors is vital for cross-confirmation of any new discoveries made. The smaller experiments use specialised detectors to concentrate on specific phenomena. These detectors are housed in vast underground caverns constructed around the accelerator ring.

Illustration 21: The CMS experiment at the LHC.

Worldwide collaborations run these experiments and analyse the resulting data. These activities do not necessarily take place on the two main CERN sites in Meyrin and Prévessin; some of them can be carried out remotely in laboratories all over the world. Ideally, the people on site work together in the same place, close to the site of the experiment. When the accelerator is running, the operators work in the control rooms.

7.2.2 Technical sites with radiofrequency systems

How do the radiofrequency systems at CERN work?

To accelerate particles, the accelerators are fitted with radiofrequency (RF) cavities, metallic chambers containing an electromagnetic field. Charged particles injected into this field receive an electrical impulse that accelerates them.

Illustration 22: One of the modules containing the accelerating cavities for the LHC.

7.2.3 Technical sites with cryogenic cooling systems

Cryogenics: extreme cold for exceptional performance

The beams containing the particles are guided around the accelerator ring by a strong magnetic field generated by superconducting electromagnets. These electromagnets are built from coils of special electric cable that operates in a superconducting state, efficiently conducting electricity without resistance or loss of energy. This requires chilling the magnets to $-271\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ – a temperature colder than interstellar space. For this reason, much of the accelerator is connected to a distribution system of liquid helium which cools the magnets, as well as to other supply services. Cryogenic technology essentially serves to cool the superconducting magnets. In particle detectors they are also used to keep heavy gases such as argon or krypton in a liquid state, for detecting particles in the calorimeters for example.

Illustration 23: Cryogenic installation at point 5 of the mounting hall of the CMS experiment.

7.2.4 Vacuum systems

From vacuum to extreme high vacuum

The LHC is unusual in that it has three separate vacuum systems: one for the beam pipes, one for insulating the cryomagnets and one for insulating the helium distribution line.

To prevent them from colliding with gas molecules inside the accelerator, the beams of particles in the LHC must travel in a vacuum as empty as interstellar space. This is called an extreme high vacuum.

In the cryomagnets and the helium distribution line the vacuum serves a different purpose. Here it acts as a thermal insulator to reduce the amount of heat that seeps from the surrounding room-temperature environment into the cryogenic parts (which are kept at 1.9 K or -271.3 °C).

Illustration 24: The vacuum at the LHC.

7.2.5 Cooling and ventilation systems

Cooling and ventilation

By cooling and ventilation we mean the design, installation, commissioning, operation and maintenance of the cooling systems, pumping stations, air-conditioning plants and fluid distribution systems for the whole accelerator complex. The equipment for the accelerator and detectors, such as the electronic racks, cryogenic installations and magnets, requires industrial water and demineralised water. Refrigerated water is needed for the air-handling units of the ventilation systems. Raw water is used in the primary cooling circuits and for firefighting. Drinking water is used for sanitary purposes. A drainage system is also required for the wastewater, which includes the water discharged and drained from the surface installations and underground areas. The other main pipeline network is for compressed air, which is used both underground and on the surface. The installations must also supply fresh air to the personnel working inside plus heating for the working environment. At the same time, the ambient temperature must be suitable for the accelerator and associated equipment.

Illustration 25: Cooling and ventilation.

7.2.6 Electrical power supply and distribution

Electrical power distribution

The electrical power distribution network supplies the whole installation including the superconducting magnets, cooling systems and detectors.

The electricity is supplied to the accelerator from the local power grid and transmitted to the electricity substations. These substations reduce the voltage to levels appropriate to the accelerator's requirements and transformers are then used to adjust the voltage.

Electrical power distribution circuits carry the electricity from the substations to the superconducting magnets, the other accelerator components and the cooling systems.

Illustration 26: Electrical transformer for the LHC.

7.3 OVERVIEW OF CIVIL ENGINEERING WORKS DURING THE FCC CONSTRUCTION AND INSTALLATION PHASES

The following plant and activities will be required to conduct civil engineering works on each of the eight surface sites:

- Earthworks to prepare the construction sites and lay the foundations for the buildings. This activity generally requires heavy hydraulically operated earthmoving plant such as excavators and bulldozers.
- Specialist shaft excavation techniques. It may be necessary to construct diaphragm walls or to freeze the ground, requiring drilling equipment and other large specialist machinery.
- The main tunnel will be excavated using tunnel boring machines. These very large machines (several hundred metres long) will bore and support the ground continuously, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. For the caverns, small tunnels and shafts through rock, hydraulic rock breakers and shearers will be used. Cranes and lifting equipment will be required above each shaft to extract the rock excavated underground.
- During the excavation of the shafts, caverns and small tunnels, the rock will initially be supported by gunite, a mix of cement and aggregate sprayed onto the exposed rock surface. This is normally reinforced by small steel fibres. This operation requires pumps, guniting machinery and the transport of raw materials underground from the surface.
- The tunnel boring machines excavate the rock, which is then transported to the surface, normally on conveyor belts. The materials are temporarily stockpiled on the surface before being transported to a permanent site or reused. If the materials cannot be reused, they will be stockpiled either close to the surface site (if appropriate locations are available) or at some distance from the site. Some materials may require treatment, for example to reduce their hydrocarbon content. This treatment may be carried out locally on the site or in special treatment facilities away from the site.
- Once the underground excavation works have been completed, concrete linings must be constructed to support the shafts, caverns and shorter tunnels. Formwork, rebar and concrete must be transported underground for this purpose. The concrete will be produced on the surface in batching plants, either in a dedicated facility at the surface site or in a third-party batching plant located near the surface site (generally less than 15 kilometres away).
- When concreting is finished, the underground elements will be painted and all metallic structures such as platforms and staircases will be installed before delivery to CERN.
- Most of the surface buildings will be constructed at the same time as the underground works and will take three to four years to complete. Tower cranes and mobile cranes will be required for the construction work.

Timescales will vary slightly for each of the eight surface sites, ranging from six to eight years approximately for the underground civil engineering works. Typical durations for each activity are shown below. It should be borne in mind that some of the activities overlap and the total duration will be less than the sum of these timescales.

- Site preparation generally lasts for 6 to 12 months.
- Excavation of the shafts, caverns and small tunnels generally takes 24 to 30 months.
- The tunnel boring will take approximately 22 months for each of the eight sectors, but eight tunnel borers will work simultaneously.
- Excavation of the tunnel alcoves and construction of the tunnel floor will take approximately a further 24 months per sector.
- Installation of the steel structures, the painting and completion work, and demobilisation will take approximately an additional 14 months.

Local and regional specialist contractors may be contracted to supply some equipment maintenance and repair services such as services relating to transport, logistics, refrigeration systems, ventilation, vacuum systems and electrical infrastructures. Furthermore, some of the equipment most commonly used on a construction site, such as scaffolding, cranes, aerial work platforms, concrete pumps and spoil sorting and treatment systems, will be supplied by local and regional contractors.

7.4 NUMBERS OF CIVIL ENGINEERING PERSONNEL DURING THE CONSTRUCTION PHASE

Illustration 27: Numbers of personnel present simultaneously on each site during each year of the construction phase.

7.5 EXPERIENCE GAINED FROM THE LYON-TURIN GRAND CHANTIER TERRITORIAL CONTRACT

The new Lyon-Turin transalpine rail link is a 270km mixed freight/passenger line between France and Italy.

Tunnel Euralpin Lyon Turin (TELT) is the binational public promoter responsible for creating and operating the cross-border section of the mixed railway line.

To aid and support the construction of this large-scale infrastructure, a special scheme designed to prepare and assist major projects was introduced: the *Démarche Grand Chantier* (Major Project Initiative)³⁰.

The *Démarche Grand Chantier*, announced by the French government back in 2003, is designed to **support this special project** before, during and after the works and to **ensure successful integration into the local area**.

A territorial contract was signed to assign responsibility for the initiative to the Prefect of the Savoie department.

The Maurienne Territorial Contract involves the French government, Auvergne Rhône-Alpes Regional Council, Savoie Departmental Council, the Syndicat du Pays de Maurienne and local authorities in the valley, in liaison with TELT, in a three-fold opportunity: hosting the project, providing economic support for the local area and providing improved transport connections in Europe by 2029. Funding totalling 40.7 MEUR was provided between 2015 and 2020 and an observatory was set up.

Outcome after three years:

Project support

The Lyon-Turin rail line: Maurienne's third-largest employer

Developing jobs and training:

- *Mon emploi Lyon-Turin*: a service for placing jobs on the project, obtaining training and recruiting future Lyon-Turin rail employees.

Supporting the local economy:

- Platform supporting the local and regional economy: a service designed to enable local and regional contractors to access the project more easily and to develop employee services.
- Rehabilitation of the public housing stock managed by OPAC Savoie.

³⁰ <https://www.telt.eu/en/>

Developing the local area

Research and development:

- Supporting the development of the Modane Underground Laboratory led by Université Grenoble Alpes.
- A future centre of competence on tunnels in Maurienne.

Energy transition:

- Construction of a wood-fired heating plant in Saint-Julien-Mont Denis and a wood store for the Modane heating plant.
- Thermal renovation of several public buildings.

Environment:

- Building of more than 160 km of cycle paths.
- Inaugural cycling festival.

Housing:

- Renovated housing to accommodate Lyon-Turin employees.
- Fifty homes already renovated in Saint-Jean-de-Maurienne.

Development:

- Renovation of the Stade Joseph Gavarini in Saint-Jean-de-Maurienne, a major sports facility.
- Redevelopment of the areas around the Saint-Avre and Modane railway stations (at the planning stage) to make them more practical and accessible.
- Some ten village centre rehabilitation programmes begun to rejuvenate communities and improve quality of life.

7.6 LOCATION MATRIX IN KM AND MIN: SITES AND OPTIONS

Table 22: Distance and duration matrix for journeys by road between the CERN sites, the FCC sites and the options.

	CERN Meyrin	CERN Prévessin	PA	PB	PD/06	PF/05	PG/01	PH	PJ/04	PL	O2	O3
CERN Meyrin	0	4.0 km 7 min	4.6 km 10 min	17.1 km 40 min	37.3 km 32 min	49.0 km 40 min	39.9 km 40 min	35.3 km 35 min	29.3 km 27 min	13.2 km 12 min	41.9 km 44 min	48.4 km 46 min
CERN Prévessin	4.0 km 7 min	0	3.6 km 5 min	21.5 km 35 min	40.9 km 35 min	52.2km 41 min	43.5 km 41 min	38.6 km 36 min	30.3 km 26 min	14.2 km 13 min	45.5 km 50 min	52.3 km 53 min
PA	4.6 km 10 min	3.6 km 5 min	0	18.6 km 40 min	38.0 km 34 min	49.3 km 45 min	40.6 km 41 min	35.8 km 40 min	34.2 km 35 min	18.2 km 21 min	39.4 km 41 min	48.8 km 44 min
PB	17.1 km 40 min	21.5 km 35 min	18.6 km 40 min	0	14.6 km 18 min	26.2 km 27 min	39.8 km 38 min	37.9 km 37 min	34.4 km 36 min	32.5 km 45 min	40.9 km 39 min	51.3 km 45 min
PD/06	37.3 km 32 min	40.9 km 35 min	38.0 km 34 min	14.6 km 18 min	0	14.5 km 12 min	28.2 km 24 min	40.3 km 31 min	38.4 km 34 min	41.2 km 42 min	33.5 km 25 min	43.2 km 32 min
PF/05	49.0 km 40 min	52.2km 41 min	49.3 km 45 min	26.2 km 27 min	14.5 km 12 min	0	13.2 km 12 min	35.6 km 30 min	50.1 km 41 min	52.7 km 47 min	12.0 km 14 min	25.2 km 26 min
PG/01	39.9 km 40 min	43.5 km 41 min	40.6 km 41 min	39.8 km 38 min	28.2 km 24 min	13.2 km 12 min	0	17.7 km 22 min	41.3 km 39 min	43.9 km 45 min	4.7 km 8 min	12.3 km 15 min
PH	35.3 km 35 min	38.6 km 36 min	35.8 km 40 min	37.9 km 37 min	40.3 km 31 min	35.6 km 30 min	17.7 km 22 min	0	15.2 km 21 min	38.0 km 45 min	15.2 km 20 min	26.8 km 29 min
PJ/04	29.3 km 27 min	30.3 km 26 min	34.2 km 35 min	34.4 km 36 min	38.4 km 34 min	50.1 km 41 min	41.3 km 39 min	15.2 km 21 min	0	21.1 km 20 min	29.6 km 39 min	37.5 km 42 min
PL	13.2 km 12 min	14.2 km 13 min	18.2 km 21 min	32.5 km 45 min	41.2 km 42 min	52.7 km 47 min	43.9 km 45 min	38.0 km 45 min	21.1 km 20 min	0	43 km 43 min	52.2 km 50 min
O2	41.9 km 44 min	45.5 km 50 min	39.4 km 41 min	40.9 km 39 min	33.5 km 25 min	12 km 14 min	4.7 km 8 min	15.2 km 20 min	29.6 km 39 min	43.0 km 43 min	0	16.7 km 23 min
O3	48.4 km 46 min	52.3 km 53 min	48.8 km 44 min	51.3 km 45 min	43.2 km 32 min	25.2 km 26 min	12.3 km 15 min	26.8 km 29 min	37.5 km 42 min	52.2 km 50 min	16.7 km 23 min	0

7.7 SWOT ANALYSIS OF LOCATION OPTIONS

Table 23: SWOT analysis of option 1 – PG Charvonnex/Groisy.

Site location	
Strengths	Scientific site PG in the same location No dwellings nearby to be affected by expansion of the site The opposite side of the FCC from CERN
Weaknesses	Requirement for a larger land area
Opportunities	Proximity of Doucy, where there is a desire for urban development centred on this area → the presence of a scientific pole would support the case for urban development
Threats	Charvonnex classified as a controlled-development commune. This would have some effect on the quality of services provided to the pole Relatively rural commune
Accessibility/Mobility	
Strengths	Good road access (D1203)
Weaknesses	Access by public transport currently limited / poor bus services Sustainable transport very little used
Opportunities	Possibility of opening a rail halt at Doucy, which would boost urban development centred on this area → the presence of a scientific facility would strengthen the case for the rail halt Desire to create cycle paths to the D1203 road (providing a cycle route to Annecy) + to railway station at Mercier (Saint-Martin-de-Bellevue)
Threats	Increase in road traffic in the area around the site
Services, amenities and shops	
Strengths	Fire and rescue centre nearby
Weaknesses	Few nearby services No conference centre
Opportunities	Supporting the development of urban centres such as Doucy and Charvonnex Chef-Lieu through partnerships between local service providers (restaurants, accommodation providers) and the scientific pole
Threats	N/A
Economy	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Few businesses present
Opportunities	Local authorities' desire to strengthen the link between producers and consumers and encourage short supply chains → the pole requires a food offer + CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area
Threats	N/A
Tourism	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Absence of tourism
Opportunities	Desire to develop a tourism economy → the presence of a scientific pole has tourism potential Desire to encourage local green tourism → science tourism can go hand in hand with green tourism by promoting local tourism
Threats	The area has a tradition of mainly locally based tourism
Education/Training	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	No universities
Opportunities	Proximity of the CNRS/LAPP research centre and Annecy university campus → promoting links particularly through the mobility offer
Threats	N/A
Housing	
Strengths	N/A

Weaknesses	Inadequate housing stock
Opportunities	Desire to expand the housing stock, particularly in Charvonnex Chef-Lieu and Doucy → possibility of contributing to the building of new housing stock or of renovating housing through a territorial contract. Plan to improve the housing offer to support the development of the Doucy area (but urban expansion must be limited)
Threats	Housing market under pressure, low proportion of vacant dwellings Increase in demand for housing if the commune does not have sufficient supply
Environment/Urban development/Agriculture	
Strengths	Rural commune with an agropastoral image
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire for food autonomy as part of Grand Annecy
Threats	Maintaining the balance between developing the local area and preserving the agropastoral nature: a difficult juggling act

Table 24: SWOT analysis of option 2 – Groisy.

Site location	
Strengths	Proximity of scientific site PG Opposite side from CERN Groisy is one centre in a development corridor. This would strengthen these centres mainly through the development of housing and the economy
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire to create new “usage” corridors connecting the three main urban centres (Le Plot, town centre, administrative centre); Le Plot is near scientific site PG Future expansion of the school in Groisy and possible building of a new school in the long term. Development of the area around the railway station
Threats	Limiting of land consumption
Accessibility/Mobility	
Strengths	Good road access (D1203) Good rail access (Groisy station (including Léman Express))
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Improving sustainable mobility (walking and cycling) Developing sustainable modes of transport (walking and cycling) by building cycle paths Building a new bypass from the D1203 towards the town centre
Threats	N/A
Services, amenities and shops	
Strengths	Fire and rescue centre nearby Development of sporting infrastructures around the two schools
Weaknesses	Few nearby services No conference centre
Opportunities	Supporting the opening of new shops and services in the urban centres
Threats	N/A
Economy	
Strengths	Le Plot-Longchamps industrial estates near site PG
Weaknesses	Few contractors present, industrial estates are small
Opportunities	Stepping up the commercial and small-business role of Le Plot-Longchamps + expansion of small-business zone + controlled expansion of retail park Encouraging the opening of local shops and services in the three urban centres (including one above the Longchamps industrial estate) Allowing farm shops to open on farms in the area
Threats	N/A
Tourism	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Absence of tourism
Opportunities	Promoting locally based tourism Encouraging the development of small-scale accommodation facilities including on farms (gîte holiday rentals) → it would also be desirable for the scientific pole to have use of tourism accommodation facilities
Threats	N/A
Education/Training	
Strengths	Presence of Groisy campus
Weaknesses	No universities
Opportunities	Proximity of the CNRS/LAPP research centre and Annecy university campus → promoting links particularly through the mobility offer
Threats	N/A
Housing	
Strengths	N/A

Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	N/A
Environment/Urban development/Agriculture	
Strengths	Rural commune with an agropastoral image
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire for food autonomy as part of Grand Annecy
Threats	Maintaining the balance between developing the local area and preserving the agropastoral nature: a difficult juggling act

Table 25: SWOT analysis of option 3 – LAPP/CNRS Annecy.

Site location	
Strengths	Proximity of scientific site PG Opposite side from CERN Presence of LAPP and land available on site to accommodate a pole Annecy: centre of the Grand Annecy urban area: developing all aspects of the centre of Grand Annecy
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire to attract young families to settle in the Annecy area Concentrating urban development in the population centres of the Annecy basin Encouraging the development of and further expansion of facilities on the university/research pole Retaining the space required to expand the university/research pole for teaching and research buildings and facilities Improving public transport provision to the university/research pole Developing synergies between the university/research pole and Les Glaisins industrial estate
Threats	Restrictions/limits on land consumption
Accessibility/Mobility	
Strengths	Good road access (A41, D916, D2201, etc.) Good rail access (Annecy station (including Léman Express)) connecting with cities in the surrounding area Good bus network from the railway station to the campus, likely to improve further Improvement in public transport provision further north along the D1203
Weaknesses	Long journey time to Geneva by public transport
Opportunities	Improving the bus network between the campus, the centre of Annecy and the Annecy area in general Desire to improve rail connections with Chambéry/Grenoble and Geneva Developing cycle paths or greenways that interconnect with neighbouring areas Improvements to the structuring of the local area through public transport provision, serving the local economy Planning and organising urban development in places that can be served efficiently by public transport
Threats	N/A
Services, amenities and shops	
Strengths	Presence of a variety of local services in Annecy Conference centre at the CESC in Albigny Possibility of holding conferences in the amphitheatre at LAPP
Weaknesses	Lack of local services on the Annecy campus and Parc des Glaisins industrial estate, particularly restaurant facilities for local working population
Opportunities	Improving local services on the Les Glaisins site + possibility of partnerships with local services
Threats	N/A
Economy	
Strengths	Thriving local economy
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire to develop the industry niches for which the Annecy urban area has a regional and national reputation (particularly engineering, mechatronics and image and multimedia technology) Desire to encourage the expansion of industrial estates, particularly at Les Glaisins (an “emblematic regional zone”) by developing services of all kinds Encouraging the implementation of a strategy designed to boost the area through innovation and by supporting creativity and the quest for excellence in the technology and corporate management industries through training and the promotion of centres of excellence

	Developing short distribution (producer-to-consumer) chains
Threats	N/A
Tourism	
Strengths	Tourism is an industry in its own right in the Annecy basin: cultural tourism, mountain tourism, lakeside tourism and water-based tourism, green tourism
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire to promote and develop Annecy's tourism appeal: encouraging and supporting year-round tourism by further developing business tourism, particularly through the exhibition, seminar and congress centre (CESC) at Albigny Maintaining and developing the accommodation offer for the long term
Threats	Snow cover becoming increasingly unreliable
Education/Training	
Strengths	Annecy campus with USMB and research centres (IAE, IUT, Polytech + LAPP, LAPTH, SYMME, IREGE) Plan to open MAPI (Maison de l'Action Publique et Internationale) to offer courses in modern languages, management, law and economics, plus research laboratories.
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Developing the innovative industry sectors in which the Annecy basin will be able to develop specialities and create jobs for graduates Desire to develop USMB in the Annecy basin through links with the other universities in the Geneva area and in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Desire to step up the area's ability to attract leading businesses by providing a higher education offer relevant to the area's specialised economic profile. Premium services and higher education will help boost the knowledge economy, a component of the economy essential to ensuring competitiveness and to maintaining a broad share of the productive economy Plans to expand the university pole and add to the university sporting facilities
Threats	N/A
Housing	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Pressure on the real estate market
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	N/A
Environment/Urban development/Agriculture	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire for food autonomy as part of Grand Annecy
Threats	N/A

Table 26: SWOT analysis of option 5 – La Roche-sur-Foron.

Site location	
Strengths	Proximity of technical site PF Reasonable proximity of scientific site PG Right distance from CERN
Weaknesses	Requires a larger site or a site closer to the urban centre (La Roche-sur-Foron)
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	Restrictions/limits on land consumption
Accessibility/Mobility	
Strengths	Good road access (A410, D1203) Good rail access (La Roche-sur-Foron station (including Léman Express))
Weaknesses	Technical site PF at Éteaux not served by public transport, poor bus network Heavy traffic on roads towards Geneva
Opportunities	Desire to develop cycle networks, particularly connecting to neighbouring communes and to Lake Geneva/Mont Blanc cycleway Desire to develop public transport provision to connect with the Léman Express rail network Desire to turn the railway station into a multimodal hub Plans to open up station to serve Éteaux side also
Threats	N/A
Services, amenities and shops	
Strengths	Presence of a variety of local services (shops, restaurants, hotels) in La Roche-sur-Foron Presence of industrial estates in La Roche-sur-Foron
Weaknesses	No services within the immediate vicinity of site PF Lack of restaurant facilities for local working population (stated requirement)
Opportunities	Desire to boost the town's urban economy by improving access to amenities and services and they way these interlink while improving offer provision → Possibility of a partnership with local services and the pole
Threats	N/A
Economy	
Strengths	A thriving agricultural economy that is resisting urban and economic pressure and is set to continue in the long term in terms of both its economic and its agronomic role La Roche-sur-Foron has led the way in creating a short supply chain of catering supplies for local schools Emergence of a social welfare economy, chiefly through the InnoVales regional economic cooperation scheme that brings together universities, local authorities, associations and local and regional businesses (St-Pierre-en-Faucigny) Strong local machining industry with training resources Diverse industrial estates
Weaknesses	Imbalance between economic activity and housing: economic activity concentrated in Switzerland and housing concentrated in France Marginal job creation Industrial estates of average quality (in terms of urban planning, architecture and image)
Opportunities	Enhancing the area's business environment through the activity of Roch'Expo conference centre Desire to benefit from a clear economic position to maintain an identity separate from the Geneva metropolis by reaffirming the Pays Rochois' role, hosting international events and strengthening its partnership with Roch'Expo with the ambition of being on a par with Palexpo in Geneva → CERN's science for all policy is implemented mainly through organising international conferences and events Desire to encourage farmers to become involved in initiatives encouraging short supply chains → the pole requires a food offer + CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area

	<p>Desire to improve how the area's industrial estates function and to encourage significant changes and efforts to optimise them (industry and retail particularly)</p> <p>Supporting and attracting economic players and improving the connections between the different centres of activity and the town as a whole</p> <p>Desire of elected representatives to boost economy activity in their area</p> <p>Desire to encourage business start-ups and support job creation in the area</p>
Threats	N/A
Tourism	
Strengths	<p>Roch'Expo: international exhibition centre: the 8th largest in France and the only one of its size in Haute-Savoie</p> <p>Tourism potential of La Roche-sur-Foron's medieval old town</p>
Weaknesses	Insufficient tourist accommodation in terms of quantity and quality (same applies to restaurants)
Opportunities	<p>Desire to develop cultural tourism and business tourism in relation to the exhibition centre, plus promotion of the local heritage</p> <p>Desire to develop a single tourism strategy promoting the Pays Rochois area as a thriving area, particularly through exhibitions</p> <p>Desire to develop leisure tourism with a diverse accommodation offer</p> <p>Desire to create a more coherent relationship between business tourism and local economic development</p> <p>Desire to use local tourism assets (tourism amenities, promoting the built and natural heritage, lively town centre) to boost the tourism economy</p> <p>Planned new Arena velodrome</p> <p>Desire to promote and boost the tourism sector, particularly "nature tourism" (possible additional income source for farmers)</p>
Threats	N/A
Education/Training	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	No universities
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	N/A
Housing	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Pressure on the real estate market
Opportunities	Desire to renovate the existing housing stock
Threats	N/A
Environment/Urban development/Agriculture	
Strengths	Well developed agricultural economy, quality cheese production with high added value (PDO and PGI cheeses)
Weaknesses	Difficulty in meeting demand for local produce
Opportunities	Desire to promote local agricultural produce + short supply chains
Threats	N/A

Table 27: SWOT analysis of option 6 – PD Nangy.

Site location	
Strengths	Technical/scientific site PD in the same location
Weaknesses	Requirement for a larger land area Too far from scientific site PG at Charvonnex Too close to CERN: possible difficulty attracting scientists
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	Lack of room and risk of conflict with the planned D903 dual-carriageway link
Accessibility/Mobility	
Strengths	Good road access (A40, D903, D1205) Planned D903 dual-carriageway link from Findrol to the Annemasse urban area and potentially on to Switzerland (Development of the D903 between the A40 and the Carrefour des Chasseurs junction) Cycle paths in development
Weaknesses	No railway stations nearby (nearest at Reignier, Annemasse and La Roche-sur-Foron) Busy commuter road traffic area
Opportunities	Planned link road should ease traffic congestion
Threats	N/A
Services, amenities and shops	
Strengths	Presence of Alpes Léman Hospital Presence of local services (shops, restaurants, hotels) Presence of industrial estates with businesses
Weaknesses	No conference centre
Opportunities	Possibility of a partnership with local services and the pole
Threats	N/A
Economy	
Strengths	Economically active area with presence of industrial estate and the Arve Valley
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	Desire to pursue a project to develop an industrial estate into one emblematic for the Cœur du Faucigny area → since the site location is already close to an industrial estate, a scientific research pole would support this endeavour Desire to encourage the purchase of local produce → the pole requires a food offer + CERN and the experiments host scientists and tourists keen to have an experience of the local area Desire to benefit from a resident economy → the presence of a scientific pole with ties to the local area would boost resident employment.
Threats	N/A
Tourism	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Little tourism appeal
Opportunities	Promoting itinerant tourism, sightseeing/heritage trails, theatrical guided tours Desire to develop centres of interest to encourage tourism Desire to have an events offer Desire to pursue the tourism policies already being implemented (industrial tourism for example) Encouraging tourism activities such as farm holiday accommodation and educational farms
Threats	N/A
Education/Training	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	No universities
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	N/A

Housing	
Strengths	N/A
Weaknesses	Pressure on the real estate market
Opportunities	Desire to renovate the existing housing stock
Threats	N/A
Environment/Urban development/Agriculture	
Strengths	Good-quality agricultural land Production of good-quality cheeses
Weaknesses	N/A
Opportunities	N/A
Threats	N/A

7.8 LAPP/CNRS PERSONNEL INVOLVED WITH CERN INFRASTRUCTURES AND PROGRAMMES

Table 28: Number of people at LAPP working on CERN experiments

ATLAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 11 scientists and lecturers conducting research 4 postgraduate students 3 post-doctoral researchers 8 electronics engineers 4 computer engineers 3 mechanical engineers
LHCb	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 scientists and lecturers conducting research 1 postgraduate student 1 post-doctoral researcher 1 electronics engineer 1 computer engineer 3 mechanical engineers
Accelerator R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 mechanical engineers

7.9 MULTICRITERIA ANALYSIS AND OPTIONS

This formula is applied to each of the options:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{13} W_i \times V_i$$

Where:

- S is the score obtained;
- W_i is the weighting given to criterion i ;
- V_i is the value given to criterion i ;

The results obtained are shown in Table 29.

Table 29: Multicriteria analysis, weighting, scores and options.

Numéro (i)	Critère	Poids (P)	Option 1		Option 2		Option 3		Option 4		Option 5		Option 6	
			PG (Charvonnex)		Groisy		LAPP/CNRS		PJ (Vulbens)		La Roche-sur-Foron		PD (Nangy)	
			Valeur (V)	Note	Valeur (V)	Note	Valeur (V)	Note	Valeur (V)	Note	Valeur (V)	Note	Valeur (V)	Note
1	Proximité site PH	0,18	3	0,54	3	0,54	2	0,36	3	0,54	2	0,36	2	0,36
2	Proximité site PJ	0,08	1	0,08	1	0,08	1	0,08	5	0,4	1	0,08	2	0,16
3	Proximité site PG	0,1	5	0,5	5	0,5	4	0,4	1	0,1	4	0,4	3	0,3
4	Proximité site PF	0,03	4	0,12	4	0,12	3	0,09	1	0,03	5	0,15	4	0,12
5	Proximité site PD	0,08	3	0,24	3	0,24	2	0,16	2	0,16	4	0,32	5	0,4
6	Proximité site PB	0,15	1	0,15	1	0,15	1	0,15	1	0,15	3	0,45	4	0,6
7	Accès routier	0,1	4	0,4	4	0,4	4	0,4	4	0,4	4	0,4	5	0,5
8	Transport public	0,1	3	0,3	4	0,4	5	0,5	2	0,2	4	0,4	3	0,3
9	Services	0,05	2	0,1	2	0,1	5	0,25	2	0,1	5	0,25	5	0,25
10	Infrastructures conférence	0,01	3	0,03	2	0,02	5	0,05	1	0,01	5	0,05	3	0,03
11	Universités	0,01	3	0,03	2	0,02	5	0,05	1	0,01	1	0,01	2	0,02
12	Secours	0,1	5	0,5	4	0,4	5	0,5	5	0,5	5	0,5	4	0,4
13	Entreprises	0,01	4	0,04	4	0,04	5	0,05	3	0,03	5	0,05	5	0,05
	Total	1	41	3,03	39	3,01	47	3,04	31	2,63	48	3,42	47	3,49